

D4.3 - REPORT PRESENTING THE RESULTS OF ALL SIMULATIONS AND DOCUMENTATION OF THE MODEL

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	
Abbreviation	Definition
BAU	Business-as-usual
CBBE	Circular Bio-based Economy
EUBB	Europe bio-based scenario
GHG	Greenhouse gas

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report has developed a series of system dynamics models to analyse the impacts of circular bio-based systems in key sectors like construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. These models assess environmental, social, and economic dimensions, capturing the complex relationships between factors such as material demand, consumption patterns, and life cycle impacts. Starting with drivers like population dynamics, the models trace a material's journey through manufacturing, use, resale or reuse, recycling, and disposal, highlighting the role of energy consumption and the importance of resource efficiency. The models also focus on product management strategies, particularly the cascading use of bio-based materials, to promote sustainable resource utilization. Each model is tailored to a specific region—Italy for textiles, the Netherlands for chemicals, and Germany for construction and plastics—allowing for detailed analysis and targeted policy development. In essence, these models serve as platforms for scenario simulations, exploring policy interventions that align with EU and regional sustainability goals.

This report analyses three scenarios—Business as Usual (BAU), Bio-Transition, and Bio-Revolution—to assess the impact of various policies aimed at advancing a circular bio-based economy (CBBE) across four key industries: construction, plastics, textiles, and chemicals. The BAU scenario projects current trends without additional CBBE ambitions, while the Bio-Transition scenario incorporates existing policy objectives to facilitate gradual progress. The most ambitious scenario, Bio-Revolution, introduces new and aggressive goals to expedite a comprehensive transformation towards full circularity and bio-based practices.

Across all industries, policies are categorised into demand-side initiatives, materials and energy efficiency improvements, material switching strategies, and enhanced recycling efforts. In the construction industry, emphasis is placed on increasing building renovation rates, improving material efficiency, substituting cement with wood-based materials, and maximising waste recycling to transform the sector into a carbon sink. The plastics industry focuses on reducing single-use plastics, boosting material efficiency, adopting bio-waste feedstocks, and significantly increasing recycling rates to lead the shift toward circularity. The textile sector targets extended product lifetime, improved energy efficiency, greater incorporation of bio-based materials, and robust waste collection and recycling systems to minimize environmental impact. Lastly, the chemicals industry aims to enhance both material and energy efficiency, increase the use of bio-based inputs, and improve waste management practices to achieve zero pollution and align with EU sustainability targets. Each scenario from BAU to Bio-Revolution represents a scaling up in the ambition of the intervention options, reflecting increasing levels of commitment towards achieving a sustainable and circular bio-based economy.

In addition to industry-specific scenarios at country level, a more comprehensive national scenario was simulated that reflects CBBE objectives beyond the industrial subsectors analysed. In this case the focus is on advancing towards full use of renewable energy sources in the power generation mix, including solar, wind, and biomass, and increasing the adoption of biofuels in the transport sector, all while aligning with stringent EU sustainability targets. This scenario also anticipates a notable improvement in energy efficiency, guided by EU directives, and a significant rise in waste recycling rates driven by enhanced policies. Crucially, the interplay between industrial practices and national strategies is considered, revealing how advancements in specific industries can influence and be influenced by national, cross-sectoral policies. By examining these interactions, this report aims to uncover the potential impacts and trade-offs of varying degrees of commitment to green technologies and practices, and related policy interventions, providing a comprehensive understanding of how these dynamics could shape the future energy, economic, and environmental landscapes in Germany, Italy, and the Netherlands.

The results indicate that transitioning to bio-based products (Bio-Transition) present a compelling economic opportunity, as the value addition generated by the CBBE significantly surpasses that of the BAU scenario. The Bio-Revolution scenario, which is characterized by a higher ambition both in curbing overall consumption and in increasing the use of bio-based products, further enhances this potential. Despite implementing more stringent measures to reduce consumption, the ambitious transition to bio-based products results in a more favourable economic and environmental outcome compared to the BAU scenario. This shift, however, requires increased biomass, the supply of which can be sourced in different, as well as sustainable ways. The following points outline the key findings and implications of this transition, emerging from the simulations created with the Green Economy Model (GEM):

Higher Value Addition from the CBBE:

- Bio-based products and practices show increased value addition compared to the Business-as-Usual scenario, both directly and via the reduction of externalities (e.g. air pollution and its impact on human health at the macro level).
- Despite existing policies aimed at reducing overall consumption (e.g. via conservation, efficiency, extended product lifetime), the value addition from the bio-based industry eventually more than offsets the loss of value resulting from lower consumption.

□ Demand for Biomass:

- Recent studies show that the growing demand for biomass can be met sustainably by utilizing marginal and abandoned land, avoiding deforestation and preserving productive agricultural areas (Elbersen, Eupan , Meijinger , & Mantel, 2025; Georgiadou, Goumas , & Chiaramonti, 2024) These underutilized lands provide an opportunity to expand biomass production while contributing to soil restoration, carbon sequestration, and environmental conservation. Strategic land-use planning, supportive policies, and community engagement are essential to achieving this balance and aligning biomass production with broader sustainability goals.
- Germany, the Netherlands, and Italy can meet their biomass production needs by repurposing abandoned and marginal lands, despite limited land resources. Our analysis shows that the biomass required in the CBBE scenarios can be produced using a portion (half to one third) of the already available marginal and abandoned land. This considers that, even if abandoned land is less productive than prime agricultural land, the total available land in each country is sufficient to meet the forecasted biomass demand. By strategically utilizing this land, these countries can ensure a sustainable bio-based transition without compromising agricultural productivity, nor increasing deforestation, supporting environmental conservation and soil restoration.

□ Trade-offs and Implications:

- While the economic benefits of bio-based products and practices are significant, careful consideration is needed to balance land use and environmental impacts, as well as reduced economic activity in relevant production and consumption sectors.
- Complementary policy to facilitate the transition (e.g. from cement to wood-based construction materials) and sustainable land management strategies may be necessary to mitigate potential negative effects on employment, as well as on forests and agricultural land, habitat quality, and avoid indirect land use changes.

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1 INTRODUCTION

A series of system dynamics models has been developed to comprehensively analyse the multifaceted impacts of bio-based circular systems within carbon-intensive sectors that have high potential to transition towards more bio-based tendencies, like construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. These models are analytical tools that evaluate the environmental, social, and economic dimensions inherent in these sectors/industries.

The models are designed to delineate the intricate interplay between various factors shaping material demand, consumption patterns, and subsequent life cycles. Starting from the fundamental drivers of population dynamics and material consumption, the models traverse the entire spectrum of a material's life cycle. This includes its utilization, potential resale or reuse, recycling prospects, and ultimate disposition, whether in landfills or through alternative pathways.

Energy consumption entailed in material production is integral to these models, accentuating the significance of resource efficiency and end-of-life management practices. A pivotal focus lies on product management strategies, particularly the cascading utilization of bio-based materials, underscoring the imperative of sustainable resource utilization.

Each industry model serves as a bespoke representative, tailored to specific geographic locales. The textile industry model is designated for Italy, the chemicals industry model for the Netherlands, and both the construction and plastics industry models for Germany. This localized approach facilitates nuanced analysis and targeted policy formulation to support the transition towards CBBE. These industry models serve as dynamic platforms for scenario simulations, enabling the exploration of diverse policy interventions in isolation or conjunction with national and regional objectives. Scenarios, defined as structured narratives or quantitative projections that represent plausible future developments based on specific assumptions, provide a systematic framework for assessing policy impacts. The envisaged scenarios aim to elucidate potential pathways for sustainable transition, aligning with overarching policy targets at both EU and regional scales.

Previous work in D4.1 established the foundation for understanding the transition from a linear, fossil-based economy to a circular and bio-based system, emphasizing its potential to contribute to multiple SDGs. It highlighted the need for both technological innovation and societal transformation, requiring coordinated policies, financial mechanisms, and new business models. A critical assessment of the environmental, social, and economic limitations of the current fossil-based economy was conducted, providing insights into the benefits of a circular bio-based system and informing the prioritization of policy actions.

Building on this, D4.2 focused on the development of models to quantify and assess the impacts of this transition. By refining assessment methodologies, D4.2 provided a framework for evaluating different transition scenarios, particularly for carbon-intensive sectors. These models serve as essential tools for analysing economic, environmental, and social outcomes, allowing for evidence-based comparisons between business-as-usual and circular bio-based pathways. This work forms the analytical backbone for subsequent assessments, ensuring that policy recommendations are grounded in robust quantitative analysis.

Building on these efforts, D4.3 presents the results derived from the developed models, offering a data-driven analysis of the transition from a fossil-based to a circular bio-based economy. By applying the refined methodologies from D4.2, this deliverable quantifies the economic, environmental, and social impacts of different transition scenarios, highlighting the potential benefits and trade-offs.

Drawing insights from the DESIGN workshop and D4.1 (Richter, Szarka, Pallaske, & Bassi, 2023), two overarching scenarios, aside from the BAU, emerge for the selected countries: the "Bio-Transition" and the "Bio-Revolution." The former underscores incremental progress, adhering to established policy frameworks and existing objectives. Conversely, the latter advocates for a paradigm shift towards a fully circular bio-based economy, characterized by ambitious and innovative policy goals, accelerating the pace and dimension of transition.

In summary, these industry models and policy variable analyses offer actionable insights and pathways toward a more resilient and regenerative future, constituting a robust framework for navigating the complexities of sustainable development within key industrial sectors.

2 SCENARIOS AND ASSUMPTIONS

This section provides details about the scenarios modelled, the policies included in each scenario for each industry sector, and the assumptions on the policy inputs in the model.

There are three scenarios considered. The baseline scenario is the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario, which assumes that the current trends continue in the future with no ambition of a circular bio-based economy (CBBE). The Bio-Transition scenario emphasises transition aspects and status quo policy objectives with a focus on implemented, existing policy goals towards a CBBE. The Bio-Revolution scenario integrates new and more ambitious goals, aiming at a rapid and broader transformation towards a fully circular bio-based economy.

The scenarios operationalised consider the policy portfolio scenarios for each industry (i.e. construction, plastics, textile and chemicals) carried out in the SUSTRACK D4.1 (Richter, Szarka, Pallaske, & Bassi, 2023). For each industry, there are specific policies and hence policy inputs. The policies are organized into four main categories, namely;

- demand side,
- material and energy efficiency,
- material switching
- and recycling policies.

A circular bio-based economy relies on these four key policy areas. Demand-side policies drive market adoption of bio-based products. Material and energy efficiency policies optimize resource use and reduce waste. Material switching policies promote bio-based alternatives to fossil-based materials. Recycling policies support waste recovery and circularity. The following section examines each category in this order.

Additionally, an EU level scenario was introduced to show the interplay between the bio-based scenarios per industry and the overall targets/policies of the EU in the area of a CBBE. The EU scenario is an extension of the Bio-Revolution scenario to the national level, covering additional areas of interventions in different sectors. The intention is to show the potential and consequences of a national circular bio-based plan and the interaction between industry and national planning.

To that end, three scenarios were developed, the first is a BAU scenario that accounts for the current directives and targets of the EU in terms of the CBBE. The second scenario (Bio-Transition) increases the biofuels transport mix to show how increased biomass demand will cause higher demand for agricultural land. The last scenario (Bio-Revolution) introduces electrification of transport to reduce the amount of biofuel required, creating a synergy with land use. See Table 1 for an overview.

Table 1: Overview of scenarios

Scenario	Definition
Business-as-usual (BAU)	The BAU represents a baseline projection of future developments assuming no significant changes in current policies, technologies, or market trends.

Bio-transition	The Bio-Transition scenario reflects a shift towards a bio-based economy, aligned with current EU policies and trends, emphasizing sustainable biomass use, circular economy principles, and reduced dependence on fossil resources.
Bio-revolution	The Bio-Revolution scenario represents a highly ambitious transformation towards a bio-based economy, implementing a broader and more intensive set of policies that exceed current EU trends, accelerating sustainability, circularity, and deep decarbonization across multiple sectors.

2.1 Construction industry

In the construction industry, six policies are outlined and categorized into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as shown in

Table 2. For this Industry, there is a distinct focus on increasing the use of bio-based products to shift from being a carbon source to becoming a carbon sink, based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 62 and Table 63). The goal is to boost both raw material productivity and the utilization of secondary materials to enhance the circularity of material flows and decrease reliance on non-abiotic resources.

In relation to the demand policies, the increase in the annual share of building renovation policy aims to renovate 2% of the buildings by 2030 and 4% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and a higher ambition as assumed for the Bio-Revolution scenario, being the renovation rate 3% by 2030 and 6% by 2050. These shares are established based on the policies in the Bio-Transition scenario (see Table 46 from D4.1) that propose “At least 2% of annual energy renovation in buildings” (European Commission, 2020) and “(...) renovate 3% of their buildings’ floor space annually” (European Commission, 2021) by 2030. As the model is focused on the building construction process and not the building energy use, the policy was reinterpreted as the increase in the building renovation rate, resulting in efficiency improvement.

For the efficiency policies category, the increase in material efficiency policy is set up for the Bio-Transition scenario to be 1.5% per year by 2030 and 1% per year by 2050, for the Bio-Revolution scenario the ambition increases to 2% per year by 2030 and 1% per year by 2050. These policy inputs come from the policy goals (see Table 62) “Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year” for the Bio-Transition scenario and “Improve materials productivity at 2% per year” for the Bio-Revolution scenario (BMUV, 2020). The goal was adapted to be accomplished in 2030 for the Bio-Transition scenario and then the ambition increased for the Bio-Revolution scenario, following the nature of this last scenario. The decrease of the rate to 1% in the long term for both scenarios

corresponds to a reality assumption that the material efficiency in the construction sector can have limitations.

The policy of swapping cement for wood-based materials is owed to two policy goals, namely: “(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...)”, which highlights that the “role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink” (European Commission, 2021) and the other policy goal “climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and about the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use” (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019). The policy input, the share of cement replaced by wood, has been established by the modelling team as there is a lack of a numerical indication for such goals. For the Bio-Transition scenario, the share is to be 15% in 2030 and 30% in 2050, and for the Bio-Revolution scenario, it is to be 20% by 2030 and 40% by 2050.

Finally, for the recycling policies category, the three interventions regarding waste collection, recycled materials and reused materials are based on the following set of policies from D4.1 (see Table 62):

- “The preparing for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled” (European Commission, 2023).
- Article 11 (2a) “(...) (b) by 2020, the preparation for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;” (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008).
- “The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. Specifically, for the three heaviest material categories used to construct a building, it must be ensured that for bio-based materials a maximum of 80% and for non-bio-based plastic a maximum of 50% of the total material comes from primary raw material (European Commission, 2023).
- “The use of primary raw material in building renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, a maximum 90% comes from primary raw material. For non-bio-based plastic in 75%” (European Commission, 2023).

These policy goals indicate mostly inputs for material recycling preparation and secondary raw materials use. As they are not indicating directly the shares of waste to be collected, recycled and reused, the modelling team has reinterpreted the values provided in light of the BAU shares and established the next values:

- The share of waste collection increases from 70% by 2024 to 100% by 2045 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and increases to 100% a bit earlier (by 2040) in the Bio-Revolution scenario.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 70% by 2024 to 90% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and increases to 95% by 2050 in the Bio-Revolution scenario. The fact that the share does not increase to 100% in any scenario provides a realistic perspective of the material flows, as not all waste can be recycled.
- The share of waste for reuse or to be resold decreases from 15% by 2024 to 5% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and to 2.5% by the same year in the Bio-Revolution scenario as a result of the increase in the recycling rate. The rest of the share goes to the landfill.

Table 2: Scenario's assumptions for a circular bio-based economy in the construction industry - Germany

Policy targets	BAU scenario	Bio-Transition scenario	Bio-Revolution scenario
Demand (Buildings renovation)	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 2%/year 2050 -> 4%/year	Annual share of buildings for renovation: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 3%/year 2050 -> 6%/year
Efficiency (Improve materials productivity)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 1.0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 2.0%/year 2050 -> 1.0%/year
Switching (Wood-based materials)	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%	Share of material consumption (cement) replaced by wood: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 20% 2050 -> 40%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 70% 2050 -> 70% Share of materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2050 -> 70% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16% 2024 -> 15% 2050 -> 15%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 80% 2045 -> 100% Share of materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 70% 2040 -> 82% 2050 -> 90% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16% 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 15% 2040 -> 9% 2050 -> 5%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 85% 2040 -> 100% Share of materials to be recycled: 2000 -> 56% 2019 -> 68% 2024 -> 70% 2030 -> 78% 2040 -> 88% 2050 -> 95% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2000 -> 22% 2019 -> 16% 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 11% 2040 -> 6% 2050 -> 2.5%

2.2 Plastics industry

In the plastics industry, seven policies are detailed and classified into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as depicted in Table 3. These policies aim to raise ambition and underscore the significance of the sector for the circular economy. Accelerating the transition to alternative feedstocks, refining recycling quotas, and specifying content quotas for non-fossil-based materials could serve as a model for other sectors, leading the path toward a circular, bio-based economy. The policy inputs used are based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 64 and Table 65).

Regarding the demand policies for the plastic industry, they are designed to decrease or discourage the demand for plastics in the future. The first policy is the ban on single-use plastics, which will bring a reduction of plastic products consumption. The policy input for the model is the percentage of demand reduction, which for the Bio-Transition scenario will be an 8% reduction by 2030 and 15% by 2040; and for the Bio-Revolution scenario, the percentage reduction is 10% by 2030 and 20% by 2040. The policy is included due to the next policy goal: “Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic” (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019). As the policy goal does not suggest a numerical policy input, the modelling team has assumed the percentages considering that there will be a smooth transition for the plastics demand decrease. The second demand-related policy is the percentage decrease in plastic demand by 1,5% from 2030 onwards in the Bio-Revolution scenario, which corresponds directly to the policy goal for Germany that suggests an annual reduction in growth of plastic of 1,5 %/year (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018). This goal has not been established and hence not modelled for the Bio-Transition scenario.

For the efficiency policies category, the increase in material efficiency policy is set up for the Bio-Transition scenario to be 1.5% per year from 2025 and for the Bio-Revolution scenario, the ambition increases to 2% per year from 2025. These policy inputs come from the policy goals for Germany: “Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year” for the Bio-Transition scenario and “Improve materials productivity at 2% per year” for the Bio-Revolution scenario (BMUV, 2020). The goal was established from 2025 for the plastic industry as the material efficiency for plastics has the potential to evolve fast due to technology in manufacturing processes and material types.

In the case of material switching policies, the model uses the share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste as a policy input, assuming for the Bio-Transition scenario a share of 14% by 2030 and 26% by 2040, and for the Bio-Revolution scenario the same shares for earlier years: 14% by 2028 and 26% by 2035. These shares have been set up considering the next policies portfolio while at the same time adjusting the shares to a smooth transition for material consumption.

- Use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023).
- From 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component (‘PET bottles’) contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).
- From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).
- From 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).
- Article 7: From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).

- From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilization).

It is important to note that the policy portfolio states the shares for recycled materials for specific plastic products categories (e.g. non-contact sensitive packing). Nevertheless, the ballpark values used for creating the shares are 35% by 2028 and 65% by 2040. As packing plastics share among all plastics is around 40% (European Environment Agency, 2023), when 35% is applied to the 40% results in 14% and when 65% is applied to the 40% results in 26%.

Lastly, the recycling policies have been established as next:

- The share of waste collection will increase from 73% by 2024 to 90% by 2050 for both the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 55% by 2024 to 80% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and increases to 95% by 2050 in the Bio-Revolution scenario. The fact that the share does not increase to 100% in any scenario provides a realistic perspective of the material flows, as not all plastic waste can be recycled.
- The share of waste for reuse or to be resold decreases from 15% by 2024 to 1.5% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario, and to 4.8% by the same year in the Bio-Revolution scenario as a result of the increase in the recycling rate. The rest of the share goes to the landfill. For instance, in the Bio-Revolution scenario, only 0.2% of the plastic waste will go to the landfill.

These policy inputs are set up based on the following inputs:

- “Member states shall set up separate collection for at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass” (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018).
- “By 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- “By 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Increase recycling quota for plastics by 2025: 3,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
- “Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 7,5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040” (European Commission, 2023).
- “Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets
(c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated;
(d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 60 % of plastic; (ii) 35 % of wood” (European Environment Agency, 2022b).
- Increase recycling quota for plastics by 2030: 8,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).

- Mechanical recycling 45% and chemical recycling of 15%. Adapted from Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany (2021) & Transition Agenda - Circular Economy (2018).
- Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilization).

It is important to notice that the shares are not used directly as they point in general to a more specific subset of plastic products, which is packing products. As the model uses aggregated values, we adapt the shares to total plastic products while being consistent with a smooth and feasible progression.

Table 3: Scenario's assumptions for a circular bio-based economy in the plastics industry - Germany

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	Bio-Transition scenario	Bio-Revolution scenario
Demand (Ban of products and demand decrease)	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2040 -> 0%/year Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 8%/year 2040 -> 15%/year Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2040 -> 0%/year	Percentage decrease in plastic consumption due to single-use plastics ban: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 10%/year 2040 -> 20%/year Percentage decrease in plastic demand: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 15%/year 2050 -> 15%/year
Efficiency (Improve materials productivity)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 1.5%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 2%/year 2050 -> 2%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 14% 2040 -> 26%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2028 -> 14% 2035 -> 26%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 73% 2050 -> 73% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2050 -> 55% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 11% 2050 -> 11%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 90% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2030 -> 59% 2050 -> 80% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 1.5%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 73% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 90% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 55% 2030 -> 62% 2050 -> 95% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 15% 2030 -> 9% 2050 -> 4.8%

2.3 Textile industry

In the textile industry, six policies are detailed and classified into demand, efficiency, switching, and recycling, as illustrated in Table 4. The industry emphasizes the importance of waste stream separation to enhance resource efficiency by minimizing waste and disposal, based on the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 66 and Table 67). Setting specific quantitative targets for incorporating recycled products and sustainable textiles into value chains further supports the sector's transformation.

In the textile industry, the demand policy is focused on the lifetime of the products. In the Bio-Transition scenario, product lifetimes extend from 3.6 years in 2024 to 4 years by 2030 and 4.5 years by 2050. In the Bio-Revolution scenario, product lifetimes similarly start at 3.6 years in 2024, increasing more significantly to 4.2 years by 2030 and reaching 5 years by 2050. This policy is inspired by the next policy portfolio and modelled considering the materials and product flows of the model that can support such portfolio:

- “Establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects” (European Commission, 2022).
- “To support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products” (European Commission, 2022).
- “The strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts” (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).

Regarding efficiency policies, the policy modelled is focused on energy efficiency as a way to account for the policy goal: “(...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO₂ in the non-ETS sectors” (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022). The Bio-Transition scenario shows no annual increase in energy efficiency by 2024, then improves by 1% annually by 2030, and slows to a 0.5% increase per year by 2040. The Bio-Revolution scenario mirrors this pattern initially, with no increase in 2024, a 1% annual improvement by 2030 and results in 0.8% annual increase by 2040. As the policy goal is general for the energy sector in Italy, the modelling of the energy efficiency policy has been set up by the modelling team based on experience and feasible energy efficiency pathways.

For switching to bio-based materials, both scenarios start with 0% of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials in 2024. By 2030, the Bio-Transition scenario achieves a 10% replacement, growing to 20% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario is more ambitious, reaching a 15% replacement by 2030 and 30% by 2050. For this policy input, the baseline policy goals are focused on eco-designs and bio-based fibres, such as:

- “...establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects” (European Commission, 2022).
- The adapted or added policy goal: supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer).
- The adapted or added policy goal: The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%.
- Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles.

Finally, the recycling policies have been set up as follows:

- The share of waste collection for the Bio-Transition Scenario will increase from 10% by 2024 to 40% by 2030 and 80% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario starts the same but aims for 100% waste collection by 2050.
- The share of waste recycled increases from 10% by 2024 to 40% by 2050 in the Bio-Transition scenario and increases to 70% by 2050 in the Bio-Revolution scenario.
- The share of materials to be resold or reused in the Bio-Transition scenario is 5% in 2024, 10% by 2030, and 20% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario aims higher, with 5% in 2024, 15% by 2030, and 30% by 2050. The rest of the share goes to the landfill.

These policy inputs are set up based on the following inputs, considering feasible shares that are correspondent to the current situation (BAU):

- Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collections by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
- Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs" (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
- Adapted or added policy goal: 30% of resources, materials and products placed on the textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 10% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused after collection.
- Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 50% of resources, materials and products placed on the market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.
- Adapted or added policy goal: 15% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused in the after collection.
- Adapted or added policy goal: Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion.
- The development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).
- Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017).
- Adapted or added policy goal: Full circular textile material flows.

Table 4: Scenario's assumptions for a circular bio-based economy in the textile industry - Italy

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	Bio-Transition scenario	Bio-Revolution scenario
Demand (Extension of product lifetime)	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 3.6 years 2050 -> 3.6 years	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 4 years 2050 -> 4.5 years	Product lifetime: 2024 -> 3.6 years 2030 -> 4.2 years 2050 -> 5 years

Efficiency (Improve in energy efficiency)	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.5%/year	Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.8%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 10% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2050 -> 10% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2050 -> 5%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 80% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 20% 2050 -> 40% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 100% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 10% 2030 -> 50% 2050 -> 70% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 5% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%

2.4 Chemical industry

In the chemicals industry, six policies are outlined and categorized into efficiency, switching, and recycling, as depicted in Table 5. The industry aims for higher proportions of non-fossil-based carbon in material flows as a primary objective, as portrayed in the policy portfolio scenarios prepared in D4.1 (see Table 68 and Table 69). This aligns with achieving the zero-pollution target sooner, reducing concerning substances in recycled materials, and meeting overarching EU-level goals.

Initially, the chemical sector envisages both energy and materials efficiency. In the case of material efficiency, in the Bio-Transition scenario there is an improvement of 1% annual increase by 2030 and a 0.5% increase by 2050. In the Bio-Revolution scenario, material efficiency shows a 1.5% annual increase by 2025 and then a 0.5% increase by 2050. The policy is modelled based on the next policy portfolio:

- reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 50% by 2030 (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).
- reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 75% by 2050 (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).

The energy efficiency policy shows the same pattern for annual improvement rate as the materials efficiency policy. This policy is modelled as a result of the general policy goals for emissions reduction and pollution: Reduction of 5 Mt of CO₂ emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021) & 0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020).

For switching to bio-based materials, both scenarios start with 0% of material consumption replaced by bio-based materials in 2024. By 2030, the Bio-Transition scenario achieves a 10% replacement, growing to 20% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario is more ambitious, reaching a 15% replacement by 2030 and 30% by 2050. This policy is inspired by the policy goal: “Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50%” (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).

For the recycling policies around waste collection, recycling and reuse, they are based on the general policy goals: “To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimized” (European Commission, 2020) & “In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular” (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023). As the policy goals lack detail on collection, recycling and reuse quotas, the modelling team has made the following assumptions:

- The percentage of waste collection in the Bio-Transition scenario is 60% in 2024, increasing to 75% by 2030 and 90% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario starts the same but aims for 80% by 2030 and 95% by 2050.
- The share of materials to be recycled in the Bio-Transition scenario is 16% in 2024, rising to 30% by 2030 and 60% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario increases recycling to 40% by 2030 and 75% by 2050.
- The share of materials to be resold or reused in the Bio-Transition scenario is 1.92% in 2024, 15% by 2030, and 35% by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario aims for 15% by 2030 and 25% by 2050, starting at 1.92% in 2024.

Table 5: Scenario’s assumptions for a circular bio-based economy in the chemicals industry - Netherlands

Policy/scenario	BAU scenario	Bio-Transition scenario	Bio-Revolution scenario
Demand			
Efficiency (Improve materials and energy efficiency)	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 0%/year 2050 -> 0%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1%/year 2040 -> 0.5%/year	Annual percentage increase in material efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2025 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year Annual percentage increase in energy efficiency: 2024 -> 0%/year 2030 -> 1.5%/year 2050 -> 0.5%/year
Switching (bio-based materials)	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 0% 2050 -> 0%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 10% 2050 -> 20%	Share of material consumption replaced by bio-waste: 2024 -> 0% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 30%
Recycling (Material recycling at the end of life)	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 60% 2050 -> 60% Share of materials to be recycled:	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 75% 2050 -> 90% Share of materials to be	Percentage of waste collection: 2024 -> 60% 2030 -> 80% 2050 -> 95% Share of materials to be recycled: 2024 -> 16%

	2024 -> 16% 2030 -> 16% 2050 -> 16% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 1.92% 2050 -> 1.92%	recycled: 2024 -> 16% 2030 -> 30% 2050 -> 60% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 35%	2030 -> 40% 2050 -> 75% Share of materials to be resold or reused: 2024 -> 1.92% 2030 -> 15% 2050 -> 25%
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2.5 National Scenarios

In the following section, we delve into the assumptions underlying the national scenarios, which are crucial for understanding the pathways each country might take towards achieving sustainability goals. These assumptions provide the foundation for analysing how different levels of bio-based products and practices adoption, electrification, and industrial innovation could shape the future energy and economic landscape at the national level. By exploring these scenarios, we gain insights into the potential impacts and trade-offs associated with varying degrees of commitment to the CBBE across different countries. The scenarios introduce a switch to renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and biomass), increased use of biofuels in the transport sector, reduction in waste, and the higher value addition from the specific national industry under the Bio-Revolution scenario.

2.5.1 Germany

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario the power generation capacity in Germany mainly relies on coal, and wind power. To simulate the shift towards more bio-based technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar and wind are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios Table 6.

Table 6: Power Generation shares in Germany

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	2.22%	BAU: 2.22% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0.00%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	16.2%	BAU: 16.2% EUBB: 0%
Coal	29.7%	BAU: 29.7% EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	11.7%	BAU: 11.7% EUBB: 11.5%

Biomass	7%	BAU: 7% EUBB: 13%
Hydropower Large Scale	4.2%	BAU: 4.2% EUBB: 13%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Solar Large Scale	8.4%	BAU: 8.4% EUBB: 22.4%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	15.3%	BAU: 15.3% EUBB: 32.3%
Wind offshore	4.1%	BAU: 4.1% EUBB: 4.1%
Waste Generation	1%	BAU: 4.1% EUBB: 4.1%
Geothermal	0.04%	BAU: 0.04% EUBB: 0.04%

Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals, but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, Germany's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the European Union's bio-based scenario, which emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that, driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Germany's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport sector, focusing on transition to using more biofuels instead of the traditional petroleum-based products. In the EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use, 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU bio-based low transport) scenario is to by 2030 have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and bio-based transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

2.5.2 Italy

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario the power generation capacity in Italy mainly relies on Gas turbines (50% in 2022). To simulate the shift towards more bio-based technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar, wind, and hydro are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios Table 7.

Table 7: Power Generation shares in Italy

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	3.7%	BAU: 3.7% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	49.8%	BAU: 49.8% EUBB: 0%
Coal	5.5%	BAU: 5.5% EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Biomass	5.8%	BAU: 5.8% EUBB: 15.8%
Hydropower Large Scale	16.4%	BAU: 16.4% EUBB: 50.4%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%

Solar Large Scale	8.7%	BAU: 8.7% EUBB: 21%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	7.2%	BAU: 7.2% EUBB: 10.4%
Wind offshore	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Waste Generation	0.8%	BAU: 0.8% EUBB: 0.8%
Geothermal	2.1%	BAU: 2.1% EUBB: 2.1%

Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals, but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, Italy's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the EU bio-based scenario, which emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that, driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Italy's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport section, focusing on transition to using more biofuels instead of the traditional petroleum. In the EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use, 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU bio-based low transport) scenario is to by 2030 have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and

bio-based transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

2.5.3 Netherlands

Power generation sector

In the BAU scenario, the power generation capacity in the Netherlands mainly relies on Gas turbines (50% in 2022). To simulate the shift towards more bio-based technologies, the shares for conventional fossil fuels are reduced towards 0, while biomass, solar, wind, and hydro are increased to show a transition to almost full renewables by 2050. The share of generation in 2050 remains the same for all national scenarios Table 8.

Table 8: Power Generation shares in the Netherlands

Power Generation Technology	Share of Generation in 2022	Share of Generation in 2050
Diesel and Fuel Oil	3.15%	BAU: 3.15% EUBB: 0%
Cogeneration	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Gas Turbine	46.37%	BAU: 46.37% EUBB: 0%
Coal	14.21%	BAU: 14.21% EUBB: 0%
Nuclear	3.13%	BAU: 3.13% EUBB: 0%
Biomass	7.1%	BAU: 7.1% EUBB: 12%
Hydropower Large Scale	0.07%	BAU: 0.07% EUBB: 3%
Hydropower Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Solar Large Scale	9.41%	BAU: 9.41% EUBB: 40.41%
Solar Small Scale	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%
Wind onshore	8.2%	

		BAU: 8.2% EUBB: 36.23%
Wind offshore	6.51%	BAU: 6.51% EUBB: 6.51%
Waste Generation	1.8%	BAU: 1.8% EUBB: 1.8%
Geothermal	0%	BAU: 0% EUBB: 0%

Furthermore, an additional 1% improvement per year in energy efficiency is anticipated, in line with the European Union's directive aimed at enhancing overall energy performance and sustainability. This incremental increase reflects the EU's broader strategy to optimize energy production and consumption, promoting more efficient technologies and practices across various sectors. The focus on energy efficiency not only supports the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the achievement of long-term environmental and economic goals, but also stimulates economic growth via higher energy productivity.

Waste Recycling

In the BAU scenario, the Netherlands's recycling rate for municipal waste is projected to remain at a modest 16% on a national scale. This figure reflects current practices and regulatory frameworks that have yet to significantly advance. However, in the EU bio-based scenario, which emphasizes a shift towards more sustainable waste management practices and adherence to stringent EU recycling targets, there is a substantial expectation for improvement. This scenario anticipates that, driven by enhanced recycling initiatives and stricter environmental policies, Italy's recycling rate will rise significantly to 77% by the year 2035. This improved recycling rate is not changed for the various national level scenarios.

Transport

Several assumptions are made within the transport section, focusing on transition to using more biofuels instead of the traditional petroleum. In the EU's minimum targets for renewable energy and specifically fuel use, 3.5% of the fuel mix should be from biofuels by 2030 (European Commission, 2024). Hence, the original target for the EUBB_lowtransport (EU bio-based low transport) scenario is to by 2030 have shifted 3.5% of energy consumption in the transport sector to biofuels. However, an additional scenario is run with the transition increased to 25% to highlight the increased demand that such an ambition target can incur. To mitigate the increased land demand due to high levels of biofuel consumption in the transport sector, a new simulation with 60% of transport consumption being electrified is run to see when policies for electrification and bio-based transitions are run simultaneously, whether the high demand for land for biomass can be mitigated.

3 RESULTS

This section offers a comprehensive evaluation of the multifaceted impacts of transitioning to a CBBE across key industrial sectors—construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles. Utilising a series of system dynamics models embedded in the Green Economy Model (GEM), this analysis investigates the environmental, social, and economic dimensions of these industries within specific geographic contexts. By simulating various scenarios, including the incremental "Bio-Transition" and the ambitious "Bio-Revolution," the models offer critical insights into material demand, energy consumption, resource efficiency, and policy interventions. This section aims to illuminate potential pathways for sustainable development, aligning with both national and regional objectives for a more resilient future.

The simulations are structured into two key components: (1) the national-level model, which determines the activation of CBBE policies, and (2) the sectoral model embedded in GEM, which defines the specific industry scenario. The naming convention reflects these elements. The first part of the scenario name specifies the national-level setting, while the second part indicates the sectoral model applied.

Table 9: Scenario naming convention and description

Scenario	Description
BAU EU + BAU Industry	Business-as-usual for both the national model and industry sub-model.
BAU EU + BioTrans Industry	BAU at the national level, with a bio-transition scenario for industry.
BAU EU + BioRev Industry	BAU at the national level, with a bio-revolution scenario for industry.
EUBB_lowtransport + BioRev Industry	EU biobased scenario with 3.5% transport shift to biofuels + bio-revolution industry.
EUBB_hightransport + BioRev Industry	EU biobased scenario with 25% transport shift to biofuels + bio-revolution industry.
EUBB_hightransport_elec + BioRev Industry	EU biobased scenario with 25% transport shift to biofuels + 60% transport electrification + bio-revolution industry.

The BAU EU + BAU Industry scenario serves as the reference case, while more ambitious scenarios progressively introduce CBBE policies, shifts in transport fuels, and electrification, increasing bio-based integration. The following sections analyse the impact of these variations in detail.

3.1 Construction industry

The construction sector in Germany plays a critical role in the nation's economy, serving as a key driver of growth and employment. As one of the largest industries in the country, it is heavily influenced by various factors, including demographic changes, technological advancements, and evolving environmental policies. The sector's future trajectory is being shaped by these dynamics, with potential scenarios ranging from traditional business practices to more innovative, sustainable approaches. This analysis explores the projected value addition in Germany's

construction sector under different scenarios, highlighting the economic impacts of transitioning towards bio-based products and sustainable practices.

3.1.1 Value Addition

Value addition in a circular biobased economy refers to the process of transforming raw materials into higher-value products through sustainable methods. By analysing value addition, we can assess the potential growth that a transition to a CBBE can provide. This analysis helps to uncover the economic benefits of such a transition, illustrating how adopting sustainable practices can drive overall economic growth and create new opportunities.

Under the Business-as-Usual (BAU) assumptions, the value addition from the construction sector in Germany is estimated to be 141 billion EUR in 2024. This figure is expected to increase by 6.3%, reaching 150 billion EUR by 2050. The anticipated growth can be attributed to the dual effects of a declining population and an overall rise in value addition within the sector, despite demographic challenges.

In contrast, under the Bio-Transition scenario, the real construction GDP for Germany is projected to experience a more substantial increase, reaching 169 billion EUR by 2050. This scenario reflects a strategic shift towards more sustainable practices and bio-based products, which contribute to this moderate yet significant growth in the sector's economic output.

Furthermore, if the Bio-Revolution scenario is implemented, the value addition from the construction sector is expected to reach 177 billion EUR by 2050 (Figure 1). This scenario envisions a higher level of ambition in transitioning to bio-based products, thereby driving even greater economic growth within the construction industry compared to the Bio-Transition scenario. The enhanced focus on sustainability under this scenario underscores the potential for substantial economic benefits when adopting more innovative and eco-friendly approaches in the construction sector.

Figure 1: Construction value addition under various scenarios

3.1.2 Production & Material Consumption

Production and material consumption are essential aspects of the CBBE, focusing on how resources are used and transformed during production. The goal is to reduce waste and optimize the use of renewable materials, promoting a more sustainable and efficient economy. By analysing production and material consumption within the CBBE, we can identify opportunities to minimize resource use, enhance sustainability, and improve overall economic performance.

In the BAU scenario, Germany's construction sector faces a decline in both construction rates and material consumption due to demographic shifts and limited recycling efforts. The construction rate is expected to decrease from 113 million m² per year in 2024 to 95 million m² by 2050, with material consumption dropping from 126 million tons to 96 million tons annually during the same period. Under the Bio-Transition scenario, increased focus on renovating existing buildings and implementing policies for recycling, reusing, and reducing consumption leads to further reductions. The construction rate declines to 91 million m² per year by 2050, and material consumption is significantly lowered to 21 million tons annually. In the Bio-Revolution scenario, even more ambitious sustainability measures drive greater reductions. The construction rate falls to 88 million m² per year by 2050 (Figure 2), while material consumption is reduced to just 15 million tons annually (Figure 3), reflecting the sector's shift towards more sustainable practices and minimized resource use.

Figure 2: Construction rate under various scenarios

Figure 3: Material Consumption under various scenarios

3.1.3 Waste and Recycling

Waste and recycling are critical elements of the CBBE, emphasizing the importance of reusing and repurposing materials to minimize waste and reduce environmental impact. By promoting efficient recycling processes and closing material loops, the CBBE aims to create a more sustainable system where resources are continuously reused rather than discarded. Analysing waste and recycling within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing waste generation, improving recycling efficiency, and contributing to a more sustainable and circular economy.

Reducing resource use by increasing material efficiency is crucial in reducing the waste generated in the construction sector. In the BAU scenario, where the building stock remains relatively steady, waste generation consistently hovers around 149 million tons per year. Concurrently, waste collection remains stable at approximately 104 million tons per year, reflecting a collection rate of 70%. This stability indicates that the current system's efficiency is maintained without substantial improvements (Figure 4).

In contrast, the Bio-Transition scenario demonstrates a more progressive approach. Under this scenario, waste generation decreases by 48.1%, falling to 74 million tons per year by 2050. This reduction is complemented by an increase in the collection rate to 100% by 2045, resulting in a total waste collection of 75 million tons per year. The combination of improved collection practices and reduced waste generation underscores the scenario's effectiveness in enhancing overall waste management.

The Bio-Revolution scenario illustrates an even more transformative impact. Here, the collection rate is projected to reach 100% by 2040, and with the implementation of additional synergistic policies, waste generation is reduced by 58.5% compared to the BAU scenario, resulting in a total of 59 million tons per year by 2050. This leads to a significant 39% reduction in waste collection, bringing it down to 60 million tons per year.

Figure 4: Total waste collection under various scenarios

In the BAU scenario, the recycling rate remains steady at 70% from 2024 to 2050, which translates to an average of 71 million tons of waste recycled per year. This consistency reflects the stable performance of current recycling practices under the existing framework. Conversely, the Bio-Transition scenario assumes an increase in the recycling rate to 90% by 2050. However, this scenario also incorporates reductions in waste generation and consumption driven by other policies. As a result, the recycling rate initially experiences a decline before rising again due to the higher recycling target. By 2050, the total amount of waste recycled under this scenario reaches 68 million tons per year.

Furthermore, the Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by more ambitious goals, initially sees an increase in the recycling rate. Nonetheless, this scenario eventually results in a significant decline, with the recycling rate falling to 57 million tons per year by 2050 due to higher waste reduction targets (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Recycling rate under various scenarios

3.1.4 Energy Consumption & Emissions

Energy consumption and emissions are key factors in the CBBE, focusing on the sustainable use of energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions throughout production and consumption processes. By transitioning to renewable energy sources and optimizing energy efficiency, the CBBE aims to lower environmental impacts and contribute to climate goals. Analysing energy consumption and emissions within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing carbon footprints, improving energy use, and fostering a more sustainable and low-emission economy.

The analysis of fuel consumption and emissions in the construction sector reveals significant differences across scenarios. In the BAU scenario, total fuel consumption in the construction sector starts at 126,454 TJ/year in 2024 and decreases to 97,056 TJ/year by 2050. Correspondingly, energy consumption releases 6.9 million tons of CO₂e in 2024, reducing to 5.3 million tons per year by 2050 (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Energy consumption in the construction industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, energy consumption is dramatically reduced by 76%, reaching 23,032 TJ/year by 2050. This scenario also sees emissions from the construction sector decline to 1.26 million tons of CO₂e per year by 2050. However, the use of biofuels leads to a modest increase in N₂O emissions, with air pollutants from the energy sector (economy-wide) reducing by 1.31% to 4.1%, depending on the pollutant considered (

Table 10).

Table 10: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Bio-Transition	Bio-Revolution

Variable	Unit	% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO2 emissions Energy sector	Ton CO2e/year	0.00%	-0.83%	-1.31%	-1.44%	0.00%	-1.11%	-1.53%	-1.60%
Total PM2.5 emissions energy sector	Ton PM2.5/year	0.00%	-1.01%	-1.67%	-2.00%	0.00%	-1.48%	-2.03%	-2.15%
Total NOx emissions energy sector	Ton NOx/year	0.00%	-1.83%	-3.35%	-4.10%	0.00%	-2.64%	-4.07%	-4.44%
Total N2O emissions energy sector	Ton N2O/year	0.00%	0.01%	0.21%	0.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.26%	0.35%

The Bio-Revolution scenario achieves even greater reductions in energy consumption, with a decrease of 82.7% to 16,826 TJ/year by 2050. Emissions under this scenario fall to 925,732 tons of CO2e per year by 2050. This scenario also results in more substantial reductions in air pollutants, with decreases being more pronounced due to the higher policy ambitions, reflecting a significant reduction in pollutants from both energy consumption and power generation at the national level (Table 11).

Table 11: Percentage difference for air pollutants from power generation under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		Percentage difference				Percentage difference			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO2 emissions power generation	Ton CO2e/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-1.95%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.18%
Total PM2.5 emissions power generation	Ton PM2.5/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.24%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.52%
Total NOx emissions power generation	Ton NOx/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.09%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.35%
Total N2O emissions power generation	Ton N2O/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.34%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.63%

Overall, the scenarios demonstrate a clear trend: increased policy ambition leads to greater reductions in both energy consumption and emissions, with the Bio-Revolution scenario achieving the most significant improvements in environmental impact.

3.1.5 Employment

Employment is a key factor in the CBBE, as the transition to more sustainable practices can create new job opportunities while also potentially leading to job declines in certain areas due to efficiency gains. While the shift towards a biobased economy is expected to generate green jobs in sectors like recycling, renewable energy, and sustainable production, it may also result in job reductions in industries where automation or more efficient processes reduce the need for labour. Analysing employment within the CBBE helps to identify both the opportunities and trade-offs, allowing for a more balanced understanding of how the transition impacts the workforce.

The employment trends within the construction sector under various scenarios reveal notable shifts. In the BAU scenario, total employment in the construction sector is 2.26 million jobs in 2024, which decreases to 1.9 million jobs by 2050. This reduction reflects a gradual decline in sectoral employment under current conditions.

In the Bio-Transition scenario, employment in the construction sector decreases further due to reduced consumption, falling to 1.82 million jobs by 2050. Despite an increase in recycling rates, the overall number of jobs still diminishes because of reduced waste generation.

The Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by more ambitious policy measures, leads to the most significant decline in construction sector jobs, with employment decreasing to 1.77 million by 2050 (Figure 7). This reflects the sector's adaptation to higher efficiency and sustainability targets.

Figure 7: Employment in the construction sector under various scenarios

Regarding recycling-specific employment within the construction sector, the BAU scenario maintains around 312,000 jobs throughout the period up to 2050. In the Bio-Transition scenario, although recycling rates increase, the total number of recycling jobs declines to 198,852 by 2050 due to a reduction in waste generation. The Bio-Revolution scenario sees a more pronounced decline, with recycling jobs falling to 154,314 by 2050 (Figure 8). This more significant decrease highlights the impact of higher policy ambitions on employment within the recycling sector.

Figure 8: Employment in the recycling construction supply chain under various scenarios

3.2 Plastics industry

The analysis of the plastics sector offers important insights into the industry's response to evolving environmental and regulatory conditions. As global concerns about sustainability and resource efficiency intensify, examining how the plastics sector adapts under various scenarios is crucial. This analysis focuses on three distinct scenarios: BAU, Bio-Transition, and Bio-Revolution. Each scenario presents different projections for fuel consumption, emissions, and employment within the plastics industry. By evaluating these scenarios, we aim to uncover the potential impacts of varying policy measures and technological advancements on the sector's operational efficiency, environmental footprint, and job dynamics. This examination will provide a comprehensive understanding of how shifts in industry practices and regulatory frameworks could influence the future of the plastics sector and its contribution to sustainability objectives.

3.2.1 Value Addition

Value addition in a circular biobased economy refers to the process of transforming raw materials into higher-value products through sustainable methods. By analysing value addition, we can assess the potential growth that a transition to a CBBE can provide. This analysis helps to uncover the economic benefits of such a transition, illustrating how adopting sustainable practices can drive overall economic growth and create new opportunities.

Under the BAU scenario, the value addition from the plastics sector in Germany is estimated to be €27 billion in 2024, increasing by 19.4% to €33.26 billion by 2050. This growth is driven by a combination of a declining population and an increase in the sector's value addition. In the Bio-Transition scenario, the real value addition from the plastics sector in Germany is expected to

reach €33.37 billion by 2050. Although the value addition initially declines due to reduced consumption, it rebounds as the sector adapts to higher recycling rates and improved efficiency. Under the Bio-Revolution scenario, marked by more ambitious goals and a transition to bio-based products, the value addition from the plastics sector is projected to be €33.27 billion by 2050 (Figure 9). Additionally, based on the trajectory, the value addition from the plastics industry will outgrow the conventional industry in the long term, but in the short term will lose some economic production due to reduced consumption through either bans or policies intended to dissuade plastic usage.

Figure 9: Plastics value addition under various scenarios

3.2.2 Production & Material Consumption

Production and material consumption are essential aspects of the CBBE, focusing on how resources are used and transformed during production. The goal is to reduce waste and optimize the use of renewable materials, promoting a more sustainable and efficient economy. By analysing production and material consumption within the CBBE, we can identify opportunities to minimize resource use, enhance sustainability, and improve overall economic performance.

In the BAU scenario, Germany’s plastic production rate experiences a modest decline from 13 million tons per year in 2024 to 12.6 million tons per year by 2050, primarily due to a declining population. Material consumption in the plastics industry remains relatively high due to lower levels of recycling and reuse. In this scenario, material consumption is 14.5 million tons per year in 2024, decreasing only slightly to 13.3 million tons per year by 2050 (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Plastic consumption under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, the production rate further declines to 10.7 million tons per year by 2050 as a result of reduced consumption. This scenario also sees significant reductions in material consumption, driven by policies aimed at enhancing recycling, reusing, and reducing consumption. By 2050, material consumption in the plastics industry is reduced to 4.3 million tons per year.

Figure 11: Material consumption in the plastic industry under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by more ambitious consumption reduction goals, results in a further decrease in plastic production to 9.9 million tons per year by 2050. This scenario also achieves a substantial reduction in material consumption, reaching 3.05 million tons

per year by 2050 due to even more rigorous policies promoting recycling and reduction (Figure 11).

3.2.3 Waste and Recycling

Waste and recycling are critical elements of the CBBE, emphasizing the importance of reusing and repurposing materials to minimize waste and reduce environmental impact. By promoting efficient recycling processes and closing material loops, the CBBE aims to create a more sustainable system where resources are continuously reused rather than discarded. Analysing waste and recycling within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing waste generation, improving recycling efficiency, and contributing to a more sustainable and circular economy.

In the BAU scenario, the waste generation from the plastics sector remains stable at approximately 10.2 million tons per year, as the stock of products in use remains relatively constant after 2024. Waste collection also remains steady at around 75 million tons per year, maintaining a collection rate of 73%. The recycling rate is constant at 55% from 2024 to 2050, translating to an average of 4.2 million tons recycled annually (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Waste collection in the plastic industry under various scenarios

In contrast, the Bio-Transition scenario introduces significant changes. Total waste generation decreases by 53.2%, falling to 5.04 million tons per year by 2050. The collection rate increases to 90%, resulting in a total waste collection of 4.5 million tons per year by 2050, driven by improved waste management practices. The recycling rate also rises to 80%, leading to 3.6 million tons of waste recycled annually by 2050 (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Recycling rate in the plastic industry under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario demonstrates even more ambitious outcomes. Here, waste generation is reduced by 59.7% compared to the BAU scenario, reaching 4.3 million tons per year by 2050. The collection rate achieves 90%, with total waste collection declining to 3.96 million tons per year. Additionally, the recycling rate reaches 95%, resulting in 3.7 million tons of waste recycled annually. This scenario reflects a higher emphasis on reducing waste generation, which slightly limits the amount recycled compared to the Bio-Transition scenario.

3.2.4 Energy Consumption & Emissions

Energy consumption and emissions are key factors in the CBBE, focusing on the sustainable use of energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions throughout production and consumption processes. By transitioning to renewable energy sources and optimizing energy efficiency, the CBBE aims to lower environmental impacts and contribute to climate goals. Analysing energy consumption and emissions within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing carbon footprints, improving energy use, and fostering a more sustainable and low-emission economy.

In the BAU scenario, total fuel consumption in the construction sector is projected to decrease from 96,691 TJ/year in 2024 to 88,499 TJ/year by 2050 (Figure 14). This reduction in energy consumption results in a decrease in CO₂e emissions from 7.8 million tons in 2024 to 7.1 million tons per year by 2050 (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Energy consumption in the plastic industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, energy consumption is significantly reduced by 67%, falling to 28,821 TJ/year by 2050. This reduction leads to a substantial decrease in emissions, with the construction sector's CO₂e emissions dropping to 2.3 million tons per year by 2050. Although the scenario results in a reduction of air pollutants from the energy sector by between 1.31% and 4.1%, the increased use of biofuels causes a rise in N₂O emissions (Table 12). Overall, air pollutants from power generation are reduced by 1.95% to 2.34% as energy efficiency improves and the industry shifts away from fossil fuels (Table 13).

Figure 15: CO₂e emissions from the plastic industry under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by more ambitious policy measures, results in an even greater reduction in energy consumption, down by 77.1% to 20,227 TJ/year by 2050. CO₂e emissions are further reduced to 1.6 million tons per year. Air pollutants also decrease more significantly under this scenario due to higher policy ambitions, reflecting a more pronounced improvement in environmental performance compared to the Bio-Transition scenario.

Table 12: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO ₂ emissions from the energy sector	Ton CO ₂ e/year	0.00%	-0.83%	-1.31%	-1.44%	0.00%	-1.11%	-1.53%	-1.60%
Total PM _{2.5} emissions from the energy sector	Ton PM _{2.5} /year	0.00%	-1.01%	-1.67%	-2.00%	0.00%	-1.48%	-2.03%	-2.15%
Total NO _x emissions from the energy sector	Ton NO _x /year	0.00%	-1.83%	-3.35%	-4.10%	0.00%	-2.64%	-4.07%	-4.44%
Total N ₂ O emissions from the energy sector	Ton N ₂ O/year	0.00%	0.01%	0.21%	0.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.26%	0.35%

Table 13: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO ₂ emissions power from power generation	Ton CO ₂ e/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-1.95%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.18%
Total PM _{2.5} emissions from power generation	Ton PM _{2.5} /year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.24%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.52%
Total NO _x emissions from power generation	Ton NO _x /year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.09%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.35%
Total N ₂ O emissions from power generation	Ton N ₂ O/year	0.00%	-1.40%	-2.28%	-2.34%	0.00%	-1.80%	-2.64%	-2.63%

3.2.5 Employment

Employment is a crucial aspect of the CBBE, as the transition to more sustainable and circular practices has the potential to create new job opportunities across various sectors. By shifting towards a biobased economy, the demand for green jobs, such as those in recycling, renewable

energy, and sustainable production, is expected to rise. Analysing employment within the CBBE helps to understand how this transition can drive job creation, contribute to skills development, and support economic growth through a more sustainable and resilient workforce.

In the BAU scenario, the plastics sector in Germany experiences a gradual decline in employment, with total jobs decreasing from 71,190 in 2024 to 67,415 by 2050 (Figure 16). This trend reflects a steady reduction in sectoral employment under current conditions. Recycling jobs within the plastics sector remain relatively stable at around 39,000 until 2050 (Figure 17).

Figure 16: Employment in the plastic industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, the shift towards reduced consumption leads to a more pronounced decrease in overall employment, with the number of jobs falling to 50,602 by 2050. Despite an increase in recycling rates, recycling-related employment declines to 24,155 due to decreased waste generation.

Figure 17: Employment in recycling from the plastic supply chain under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by higher policy ambitions, results in the most significant employment reductions. Jobs within the plastics sector drop to 46,307 by 2050. Additionally, recycling jobs decline further to 20,930 by 2050, reflecting the impact of stringent policies on both overall employment and recycling-related roles in the sector.

3.3 Textile industry

The textile industry in Italy, a key sector with significant economic and environmental impacts, is undergoing notable changes due to increasing sustainability demands. Analysing the industry under different scenarios—BAU, Bio-Transition, and Bio-Revolution—provides insights into how shifts in policies and consumer behaviour will affect production levels, material use, waste management, and recycling practices. This examination aims to clarify the potential impacts on the industry's efficiency and environmental footprint, highlighting how the Italian textile sector can adapt to and meet sustainability goals.

3.3.1 Value Addition

Value addition in a circular biobased economy refers to the process of transforming raw materials into higher-value products through sustainable methods. By analysing value addition, we can assess the potential growth that a transition to a CBBE can provide. This analysis helps to uncover the economic benefits of such a transition, illustrating how adopting sustainable practices can drive overall economic growth and create new opportunities.

Under BAU assumptions, the value addition from the textile sector in Italy is estimated to be €23.4 billion in 2024, increasing by 13.8% to €26.6 billion by 2050 (Figure 18). This growth is attributed to a combination of a declining population and rising sectoral value addition. In the Bio-Transition scenario, the real value addition from the textile sector is expected to rise to €31.75 billion by 2050, reflecting the sector's adaptation to increased sustainability practices and efficiency improvements. Under the Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by more ambitious goals and a shift towards bio-based products, the value addition from the textile sector reaches €33.7 billion by 2050. This outcome highlights the sector's significant potential for growth and transformation under higher sustainability ambitions.

Figure 18: Textile value addition under various scenarios

3.3.2 Production & Material Consumption

Production and material consumption are essential aspects of the CBBE, focusing on how resources are used and transformed during production. The goal is to reduce waste and optimize the use of renewable materials, promoting a more sustainable and efficient economy. By analysing production and material consumption within the CBBE, we can identify opportunities to minimize resource use, enhance sustainability, and improve overall economic performance.

Under the BAU scenario, Italy’s textile production rate declines from 13.83 million tons per year in 2024 to 12.3 million tons per year by 2050, driven by a declining population (Figure 19). Material consumption in the textile industry remains relatively high due to limited recycling and reuse, with consumption decreasing from 12.45 million tons per year in 2024 to 11.10 million tons per year by 2050.

Figure 19: Textile consumption under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, the production rate decreases further to 9.9 million tons per year by 2050, as product lifetimes are extended and consumption is reduced. Material consumption also significantly drops to 5.1 million tons per year by 2050, thanks to policies aimed at improving recycling, reusing, and reducing overall consumption (Figure 20).

Under the Bio-Revolution scenario, the production rate sees a more substantial decline to 9.1 million tons per year by 2050. Material consumption is reduced even further, reaching 2.15 million tons per year by 2050, due to more aggressive policies focused on sustainability and the transition to bio-based products.

Figure 20: Textile material consumption under various scenarios

3.3.3 Waste and Recycling

Waste and recycling are critical elements of the CBBE, emphasizing the importance of reusing and repurposing materials to minimize waste and reduce environmental impact. By promoting efficient recycling processes and closing material loops, the CBBE aims to create a more sustainable system where resources are continuously reused rather than discarded. Analysing waste and recycling within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing waste generation, improving recycling efficiency, and contributing to a more sustainable and circular economy.

Under the BAU scenario, waste generation in Italy's textile sector remains steady at approximately 12.2 million tons per year, as the stock of products in use remains relatively constant. Waste collection is limited, with a collection rate of 10% resulting in about 1.2 million tons collected annually (Figure 21). The recycling rate remains low at 10%, translating to an average of 120,000 tons recycled per year.

Figure 21: total waste collection in the textile industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, waste generation decreases by 35.2% to 7.2 million tons per year by 2050 due to improved sustainability practices. The collection rate increases to 80%, resulting in 5.7 million tons of waste collected annually. With an enhanced recycling rate of 40%, approximately 2.3 million tons are recycled each year by 2050 (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Recycling rate in the textile industry under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario achieves even more substantial reductions. Waste generation falls by 48.2% compared to BAU, reaching 5.8 million tons per year by 2050. The collection rate rises to 100% by 2040, leading to a fourfold increase in waste collection to 5.76 million tons per year by 2050. With a recycling rate of 100%, about 4.03 million tons are recycled annually, reflecting a significant commitment to sustainability and waste reduction.

3.3.4 Energy Consumption & Emissions

Energy consumption and emissions are key factors in the CBBE, focusing on the sustainable use of energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions throughout production and consumption processes. By transitioning to renewable energy sources and optimizing energy efficiency, the CBBE aims to lower environmental impacts and contribute to climate goals. Analysing energy consumption and emissions within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing carbon footprints, improving energy use, and fostering a more sustainable and low-emission economy.

Under the BAU scenario, total fuel consumption in the textile sector is projected to decrease from 35,829 TJ/year in 2024 to 31,958 TJ/year by 2050 (Figure 23). This reduction is primarily due to improvements in energy efficiency and a gradual decline in production rates. Correspondingly, CO₂e emissions decrease from 2.2 million tons in 2024 to 1.9 million tons per year by 2050, reflecting reduced fuel consumption (Figure 24).

Figure 23: Energy consumption in the textile industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, energy consumption is significantly reduced by 49.8% to 12,855 TJ/year by 2050. This substantial decrease is driven by the adoption of advanced technologies, increased energy efficiency, and shifts towards more sustainable energy sources. CO₂e emissions are cut down to 796,355 tons per year, thanks to these efficiency improvements and cleaner energy alternatives. However, the increased use of biofuels results in a slight rise in certain air pollutants by 0.14% to 0.19% depending on the pollutant. Despite this, the overall air pollutants from power generation decrease by 0.29% as the industry transitions away from fossil fuels.

Figure 24: Emissions from the textile industry under various scenarios

Under the Bio-Revolution scenario, which involves more aggressive sustainability goals, energy consumption is drastically reduced by 84.1% to 5,085 TJ/year by 2050. This dramatic decline is achieved through the implementation of cutting-edge technologies, comprehensive energy

efficiency measures, and a significant shift to bio-based and renewable energy sources. As a result, CO₂e emissions drop to 315,007 tons per year. The more ambitious policies also lead to a greater reduction in air pollutants compared to the Bio-Transition scenario, due to the more significant decrease in fossil fuel use and overall energy consumption (Table 14 and Table 15).

Table 14: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% differences BAU				% differences BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO ₂ emissions from the energy sector	Ton CO ₂ e/year	0.00%	-0.02%	0.05%	0.14%	0.00%	-0.08%	-0.04%	0.00%
Total PM _{2.5} emissions from the energy sector	Ton PM _{2.5} /year	0.00%	-0.02%	0.00%	0.03%	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.04%	-0.02%
Total NO _x emissions from the energy sector	Ton NO _x /year	0.00%	-0.03%	0.03%	0.14%	0.00%	-0.08%	-0.03%	0.04%
Total N ₂ O emissions from the energy sector	Ton N ₂ O/year	0.00%	0.07%	0.15%	0.19%	0.00%	0.07%	0.14%	0.14%

Table 15: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO ₂ emissions from power generation	Ton CO ₂ e/year	0.00%	-0.04%	0.09%	0.29%	0.00%	-0.10%	-0.04%	0.12%
Total PM _{2.5} emissions from power generation	Ton PM _{2.5} /year	0.00%	-0.04%	0.11%	0.29%	0.00%	-0.12%	-0.02%	0.12%
Total NO _x emissions from power generation	Ton NO _x /year	0.00%	-0.04%	0.09%	0.29%	0.00%	-0.10%	-0.03%	0.12%
Total N ₂ O emissions from power generation	Ton N ₂ O/year	0.00%	-0.04%	0.11%	0.29%	0.00%	-0.12%	-0.02%	0.12%

3.3.5 Employment

Employment is a key factor in the CBBE, as the transition to more sustainable practices can create new job opportunities while also potentially leading to job declines in certain areas due to

efficiency gains. While the shift towards a biobased economy is expected to generate green jobs in sectors like recycling, renewable energy, and sustainable production, it may also result in job reductions in industries where automation or more efficient processes reduce the need for labour. Analysing employment within the CBBE helps to identify both the opportunities and trade-offs, allowing for a more balanced understanding of how the transition impacts the workforce.

In the BAU scenario, the textile sector in Italy sees a decline in employment, with total jobs decreasing from 55,394 in 2024 to 49,418 by 2050 (Figure 25) This reduction reflects the impacts of a declining population and modest adjustments in sector activity. Recycling jobs remain stable at around 6,800 throughout this period, as recycling practices remain largely unchanged (Figure 26).

Figure 25: Employment in the textile industry under various scenarios

Under the Bio-Transition scenario, reduced consumption and increased recycling efforts lead to a more pronounced decline in overall jobs, with the total falling to 39,973 by 2050. However, the implementation of higher recycling rates results in a substantial increase in recycling-related employment, rising to 33,202 jobs by 2050.

Figure 26: Recycling employment from the textile supply chain under various scenarios

The Bio-Revolution scenario, characterized by ambitious sustainability goals, results in a further reduction in total jobs to 36,642 by 2050 due to more aggressive consumption reduction and efficiency measures. Nonetheless, the focus on extensive recycling and advanced sustainability practices significantly boosts recycling employment, with jobs increasing to 40,542 by 2050. This increase reflects the sector's enhanced commitment to recycling and waste management under higher policy ambitions.

3.4 Chemicals industry

The chemical industry in the Netherlands, a major player in both national and global markets, is facing transformative changes due to growing sustainability demands. By examining the sector under BAU, Bio-Transition, and Bio-Revolution scenarios, we can explore how shifts in production practices, material consumption, waste management, and energy use will impact its efficiency and environmental footprint. This analysis aims to provide insights into how the industry can navigate these changes and align with sustainability goals while addressing emerging challenges and opportunities.

3.4.1 Value Addition

Value addition in a circular biobased economy refers to the process of transforming raw materials into higher-value products through sustainable methods. By analysing value addition, we can assess the potential growth that a transition to a CBBE can provide. This analysis helps to uncover the economic benefits of such a transition, illustrating how adopting sustainable practices can drive overall economic growth and create new opportunities.

Under BAU assumptions, the value addition from the chemical sector in the Netherlands is projected to grow from €12.1 billion in 2024 to €19.8 billion by 2050, marking a 62% increase (Figure 27). This growth is attributed to a combination of a declining population and rising value addition within the sector, which drives up economic contributions despite relatively stable production practices.

In the Bio-Transition scenario, the chemical sector’s value addition increases more substantially, reaching €29 billion by 2050. This growth is facilitated by the adoption of enhanced sustainability practices, including improved efficiency and gradual shifts towards greener technologies and processes.

Should the Bio-Revolution scenario be implemented, the value addition from the chemical sector is anticipated to rise even further to €33.6 billion by 2050. This significant increase is driven by the sector’s transition to bio-based products and the implementation of more ambitious sustainability measures. The higher level of value addition under this scenario underscores the sector’s potential for growth and transformation in alignment with advanced environmental goals.

Figure 27: chemicals value addition under various scenarios

3.4.2 Production & Material Consumption

Production and material consumption are essential aspects of the CBBE, focusing on how resources are used and transformed during production. The goal is to reduce waste and optimize the use of renewable materials, promoting a more sustainable and efficient economy. By analysing production and material consumption within the CBBE, we can identify opportunities to minimize resource use, enhance sustainability, and improve overall economic performance.

Under the BAU scenario, the chemical production rate in the Netherlands is estimated to increase slightly from 30.3 million tons per year in 2024 to 30.9 million tons per year by 2050 (Figure 28). This modest increase is a result of the declining population, which leads to higher production efficiency. Material consumption also remains high, rising from 26.8 million tons per year in 2024 to 27.3 million tons by 2050 due to relatively low levels of recycling and reuse (Figure 29).

Figure 28: chemical production rate under various scenarios

In the Bio-Transition scenario, the chemical production rate remains stable, with no significant change anticipated, as no demand-side policies were considered due to the inherent characteristics and market dynamics of chemicals. Material consumption is significantly reduced to 16.3 million tons per year by 2050. This decrease is driven by policies aimed at enhancing recycling, reusing materials, and reducing overall consumption.

Figure 29: Chemical material consumption under various scenarios

Similarly, under the Bio-Revolution scenario, there is no notable change in production levels. However, material consumption is further decreased to 12.8 million tons per year by 2050, reflecting the impact of more ambitious policies focused on maximizing recycling and minimizing waste.

3.4.3 Waste and Recycling

Waste and recycling are critical elements of the CBBE, emphasizing the importance of reusing and repurposing materials to minimize waste and reduce environmental impact. By promoting efficient recycling processes and closing material loops, the CBBE aims to create a more sustainable system where resources are continuously reused rather than discarded. Analysing waste and recycling within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing waste generation, improving recycling efficiency, and contributing to a more sustainable and circular economy.

In the BAU scenario, the waste generation in the Netherlands’s chemical sector remains relatively constant, totalling approximately 7.8 million tons per year due to a stable product in-use stock (Figure 30). Waste collection also remains steady at around 4.7 million tons annually, with a collection rate of 60%. The recycling rate holds at 16%, translating to an average of 748,459 tons recycled per year (Figure 31).

Figure 30: Total waste collection from chemicals under various scenarios

Under the Bio-Transition scenario, waste generation decreases significantly by 32.2%, falling to 5.4 million tons per year by 2050. This reduction is supported by increased recycling and reusing practices, which drive up the collection rate to 90% and result in a total waste collection of 4.9 million tons per year. The recycling rate increases substantially to 60%, leading to 2.9 million tons of waste recycled annually.

Figure 31: Recycling rate for chemicals under various scenarios

In the Bio-Revolution scenario, waste generation is reduced even further by 43.8%, reaching 4.5 million tons per year by 2050. This scenario sees an increase in the collection rate to 95%, with waste collection decreasing to 4.3 million tons per year due to synergies with other policies. The recycling rate rises to a significant 70%, translating to 3.2 million tons recycled per year, reflecting the higher ambition and more advanced recycling policies in place.

3.4.4 Energy Consumption & Emissions

Energy consumption and emissions are key factors in the CBBE, focusing on the sustainable use of energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions throughout production and consumption processes. By transitioning to renewable energy sources and optimizing energy efficiency, the CBBE aims to lower environmental impacts and contribute to climate goals. Analysing energy consumption and emissions within the CBBE helps identify opportunities for reducing carbon footprints, improving energy use, and fostering a more sustainable and low-emission economy.

In the BAU scenario, fuel consumption in the Netherlands' chemical sector is expected to increase from 256,763 TJ/year in 2024 to 261,594 TJ/year by 2050 (Figure 32). This rise in consumption leads to an increase in CO2 emissions from 19.1 million tons in 2024 to 19.5 million tons annually by 2050.

Figure 32: Energy consumption in the chemical industry under various scenarios

Under the Bio-Transition scenario, energy consumption is significantly reduced by 48.1%, dropping to 135,737 TJ/year by 2050. This reduction leads to a decrease in CO2 emissions to 10.1 million tons per year (Figure 33). Although air pollutants from energy use are reduced by 4.28% to 10.82%, there is a slight increase in N2O emissions due to greater biofuel usage (Table 16). Overall, energy efficiency improvements contribute to a reduction in air pollutants by 3.48% to 3.54% by 2050.

Figure 33: Emissions from the chemical industry under various scenarios

In the Bio-Revolution scenario, the chemical sector’s energy consumption is further reduced by 61.4%, reaching 101,051 TJ/year. CO2 emissions drop to 7.54 million tons per year. This scenario sees a more substantial decrease in air pollutants due to the higher policy ambitions, with improvements in energy efficiency and a shift away from fossil fuels contributing to a significant reduction in overall air pollutants (Table 17).

Table 16: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO2 emissions from the energy sector	Ton CO2e/year	0.00%	-1.79%	-3.29%	-4.28%	0.00%	-2.71%	-4.36%	-5.45%
Total PM2.5 emissions from the energy sector	Ton PM2.5/year	0.00%	-3.69%	-5.65%	-5.89%	0.00%	-5.57%	-7.50%	-7.46%
Total NOx emissions from the energy sector	Ton NOx/year	0.00%	-4.25%	-8.22%	-10.82%	0.00%	-6.44%	-10.94%	-13.79%
Total N2O emissions from the energy sector	Ton N2O/year	0.00%	-0.10%	0.82%	1.85%	0.00%	-0.12%	1.15%	2.46%

Table 17: Percentage difference for air pollutants from energy sector under various scenarios

Variable	Unit	Bio-Transition				Bio-Revolution			
		% difference vs BAU				% difference vs BAU			
		2024	2030	2040	2050	2024	2030	2040	2050
CO2 emissions from power generation	Ton CO2e/year	0.00%	-1.77%	-2.86%	-3.56%	0.00%	-2.67%	-3.76%	-4.53%
Total PM2.5 emissions from power generation	Ton PM2.5/year	0.00%	-1.77%	-2.85%	-3.48%	0.00%	-2.67%	-3.73%	-4.43%
Total NOx emissions from power generation	Ton NOx/year	0.00%	-1.77%	-2.89%	-3.54%	0.00%	-2.67%	-3.80%	-4.50%
Total N2O emissions from power generation	Ton N2O/year	0.00%	-1.77%	-2.95%	-3.48%	0.00%	-2.67%	-3.89%	-4.41%

3.4.5 Employment

Employment is a key factor in the CBBE, as the transition to more sustainable practices can create new job opportunities while also potentially leading to job declines in certain areas due to efficiency gains. While the shift towards a biobased economy is expected to generate green jobs in sectors like recycling, renewable energy, and sustainable production, it may also result in job reductions in industries where automation or more efficient processes reduce the need for labour. Analysing employment within the CBBE helps to identify both the opportunities and trade-offs, allowing for a more balanced understanding of how the transition impacts the workforce.

In the BAU scenario, employment in the chemical sector of the Netherlands is projected to grow modestly from 47,803 jobs in 2024 to 48,758 jobs by 2050 (Figure 34). Recycling jobs within this sector remain relatively stable at around 24,000 jobs throughout the period (Figure 35).

Figure 34: Employment in the chemical industry under various scenarios

Under the Bio-Transition scenario, there is a notable increase in recycling jobs due to the implementation of higher recycling rates, rising to 39,384 jobs by 2050. This growth reflects the sector's adaptation to enhanced recycling practices and increased demand for waste management.

Figure 35: Employment in the recycling sector from chemical recycling under various scenarios

In the Bio-Revolution scenario, despite an even higher recycling rate, the number of recycling jobs decreases to 32,242 by 2050. This decline is attributed to a significant reduction in chemical waste generation, which, while fostering advanced recycling technologies, leads to fewer overall job opportunities in the sector.

3.5 EU CBBE Scenario

Economic sectors operate in the wider context of the national economy, and therefore, changes made at the sectoral or industrial level affect the overall national economic, social, and environmental performance. In this section, the impact of the bio-based transition or revolution at the national level is explored and assessed. In addition to the industry scenarios (Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution), there are three more simulations, where various levels of transitioning to bio-based materials and processes, and electrification were simulated to see the full impact of a national bio-based strategy and how to mitigate the negative consequences such as demand for land.

3.5.1 Germany

Germany is an industrious nation with high levels of construction and plastic production, due to high demand for both internationally and locally (Herrman, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021; Destatis, 2022; Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany, 2021). Despite being the world's second largest plastic producer and having a large building output, the combined industry only makes up 5.1% of total GDP in 2024. Highlighting the fact that a bio-based transition will affect various sectors, this section presents the results of simulations that consider an economy-wide CBBE transition.

In the BAU scenario, where existing policies continue without major changes and there is no bio-based transition in both industries, Germany's industry GDP is expected to grow from 3.15 trillion EUR in 2024 to 4.9 trillion EUR by 2050 (Figure 36). The introduction of bio-based policies at the industrial level initially decreases the specific industry value addition before becoming more valuable, as consumption is initially lowered but over time replaced by higher value output.

The Bio-Transition scenario, which assumes a shift towards bio-based industries through moderate policy adoption, results in an increased GDP, reaching 4.956 trillion EUR by 2050. While, in the Bio-Revolution scenario, which envisions more extensive adoption of bio-based technologies and structural changes in the economy, GDP slightly improves to 4.957 trillion EUR. The minimal difference from the Bio-Transition scenario suggests that beyond a certain point, additional policy shifts alone may not yield significant economic gains without deeper systemic changes. This is mainly due to the construction sector, where the gains under a sectoral CBBE transition are small relative to the total national GDP. The construction and plastic sectors, while important, may not experience large-scale economic growth from bio-based transitions alone, as its overall contribution to GDP is limited compared to other sectors. Therefore, more comprehensive and cross-sectoral strategies are necessary to drive broader economic benefits and foster systemic transformation across the economy.

The scenario with the greatest economic impact involves implementing EU-wide bio-based policies combined with electrification, resulting in a GDP of 5.426 trillion EUR by 2050—a 9.8% increase over BAU. This scenario highlights the critical role of comprehensive, coordinated policies at both the national and EU levels in maximizing the economic potential of the bio-based transition. Since

any policies adopted at the national level would affect each sector, the national transition would be more noticeable in the simulation. The largest contributor to GDP is the switch within the power generation sector towards biofuels, solar PV, and wind power since the investments into these technologies lead to more production and employment, less emissions and air pollution, as well as lower electricity costs.

Figure 36: Germany National GDP under various scenarios

Building on the national GDP projections, a similar pattern emerges when examining Germany's industry GDP under various scenarios. In the BAU scenario, industry GDP is set to grow from 1.37 trillion EUR in 2024 to 2.046 trillion EUR by 2050, reflecting steady progress without significant policy changes (Figure 37). The Bio-Transition scenario, which incorporates moderate bio-based policy shifts, projects a slight increase to 2.052 trillion EUR, showing limited economic impact from incremental changes. The Bio-Revolution scenario, driven by the bio-based transition of industries like plastics and construction, yields a minimal additional increase to 2.0528 trillion EUR, indicating that deeper changes offer only marginal gains without broader reforms. However, when EU-wide bio-based policies are combined with electrification, industry GDP rises significantly by 9.8% over BAU, reaching 2.24 trillion EUR by 2050. This underscores that the most substantial economic benefits arise from comprehensive, coordinated policy efforts, particularly when aligned with broader electrification strategies across the EU. For instance, increasing the use of biofuels can help reduce dependence on fossil fuels, while simultaneously promoting electrification can lower the overall demand for biomass. Such an integrated approach allows for a balanced energy mix, where biofuels play a crucial role in sectors that are harder to electrify, while electrification reduces pressure on biomass resources, creating a more sustainable and efficient system. By aligning these strategies, we can optimize resource use, minimize environmental impacts, and achieve broader sustainability goals. These trade-offs will be further explored in WP5.

Figure 37: Germany Industry GDP under various scenarios

In the BAU scenario, total industry employment in Germany is estimated to be 17.35 million people in 2024. This figure is expected to rise modestly to 17.79 million by 2050, reflecting a gradual increase in industry employment over the period. The projections indicate that industry employment under the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios will not differ significantly from the BAU scenario, suggesting that these bio-based transition strategies may not have a substantial impact on overall industry employment levels.

However, the EU bio-based transition scenario (EUBB) shows a slight increase in total industrial employment compared to the BAU scenario. On average, employment under the EUBB scenario is projected to be 0.63% higher than in the BAU scenario (Figure 38). This modest increase reflects the potential benefits of bio-based transition policies at the European level, although the impact on overall industry employment remains limited.

Figure 38: Germany employment figures under various scenarios

Focusing specifically on the power generation sector, the BAU scenario projects employment figures of 159,543 in 2024, with an increase to 172,336 by 2050 due to rising energy demand. Under both the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, employment in Germany’s power generation sector remains largely unchanged compared to the BAU scenario (Figure 39). This stability suggests that these bio-based scenarios do not significantly alter employment dynamics within the power sector.

In contrast, the EU bio-based transition scenarios with different levels of transport electrification present a more pronounced impact on employment in the power generation sector. In the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, employment in the power sector is projected to rise to 368,694 by 2050. This increase is further amplified in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, where employment is expected to reach 371,491 by 2050. The substantial growth in employment under these scenarios is attributable to the increased demand for electricity associated with higher levels of transport electrification.

Conversely, if the transport industry is fully electrified, the employment in the power generation sector is projected to decrease slightly to 369,659 by 2050. This reduction is likely due to the efficiency gains and shifts in energy production and consumption patterns associated with full electrification of transport.

Figure 39: Germany power generation employment figures under various scenarios

The higher levels of employment in the power generation sector come from the large investments into renewable energy (biofuel, solar, and wind). The transition to bio-based renewable energy is crucial to reduce emissions, boost economic output, and create employment opportunities. In the BAU scenario, the proportion of power generation from renewable sources remains relatively stable at around 38% throughout the period until 2050. This stable share reflects a continued reliance on renewable energy but without significant acceleration in its adoption. Both the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show no change in the share of renewable power generation compared to the BAU scenario as no policies related to renewable energy are considered nationally. In contrast, the EUBB scenarios emphasize a substantial shift towards

renewable energy. By 2050, the share of power generation from renewable sources is projected to increase significantly, reaching 87% (Figure 40). This increase is driven by the prioritization of biofuels, wind, and solar energy within the EUBB framework, reflecting a strong commitment to renewable energy and a substantial transformation in the energy mix.

Figure 40: Share of renewables in Germany under various scenarios

This significant increase in renewable energy has notable implications for energy costs. Renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, typically have stable and lower operational costs compared to fossil fuels. As the share of renewable energy in the power generation mix increases, the overall cost of electricity is expected to decrease, translating into lower energy bills for consumers and businesses.

In the BAU scenario, Germany's energy bill is estimated to be 453 billion EUR in 2024, gradually decreasing to 387 billion EUR by 2050. The Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show a similar trend, with the energy bill decreasing to 383 billion EUR by 2050 (Figure 41).

Under the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, where renewable energy is further prioritized, the energy bill is significantly reduced to 282 billion EUR annually by 2050. The EUBB_hightransport scenario, which includes a greater reduction in petroleum use, results in an even more substantial reduction of the energy bill to 271 billion EUR by 2050.

However, if electrification of the transport sector occurs, the energy bill is projected to increase slightly compared to the EUBB_hightransport scenario, reaching 279 billion EUR annually. This increase reflects the additional costs associated with the electrification of transport infrastructure, offsetting some of the savings from reduced petroleum use.

Figure 41: Germany energy bill under various scenarios

The impact of these scenarios on emissions is a critical consideration for evaluating their overall environmental effectiveness. In the BAU scenario, emissions from industrial processes in Germany are estimated to be 51 million tons per year in 2024, with a significant increase to 78 million tons per year by 2050 (Figure 42). This increase reflects the expected rise in industrial activity and associated emissions over time.

Under the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, national industry emissions are not significantly impacted compared to the BAU scenario as the two industries combined, only make up 5.1% of the national economy, and thus, the associated emissions are not going to largely impact the national statistics.

The EUBB scenarios, on the other hand, project an increase in national industry emissions due to higher economic activity. By 2050, emissions are expected to reach 85 million tons per year. This increase is attributed to the economic growth stimulated by the bio-based transition, which can lead to higher overall industrial emissions despite the increased share of renewable energy.

Figure 42: Germany national industry emissions under various scenarios

Despite a more sustainable industry, the increase in emissions is from the higher economic output (i.e. higher GDP, pushing energy demand higher) and unless there is a “green” future for the industries, be that through additional energy efficiency, CCS or reduction of waste to zero, there will always be energy use and pollution emitted.

This is important considering the potential negative consequences of switching to bio-based material and energy, such as the increased demand for land. The biomass that is used for the material or biofuel, if produced locally, may increase the need for agricultural land and depending on the source of the additional land, could result in the decrease of forest cover. It is therefore imperative that land use policies are considered in any transition, especially to make use of abandoned and marginal land (which is more than sufficient to produce the forecasted biomass demand)(Elbersen, Eupan , Meijinger , & Mantel, 2025)). Additionally, other options can include cascade use, increased efficiency, smart agriculture, vertical gardening, and use of residues and byproducts to limit the potential impact that bio-based policies may have on land use.

In the BAU scenario, the area of agricultural land is estimated to be 16.5 million hectares in 2024, decreasing slightly to 16 million hectares by 2050. This reduction reflects ongoing trends in agricultural land use without major shifts in policy (Figure 43).

In the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, agricultural land increases to 16.14 million hectares by 2050. This increase is driven by higher demand for biomass to support bio-based energy and products. The need for additional land to cultivate biomass crops reflects the growing emphasis on renewable energy sources in these scenarios. On the other hand, this land could be obtained from converting abandoned and marginal agricultural land, resulting in no conversion of existing, and productive agricultural land, nor deforestation.

The EUBB_hightransport scenario requires even more agricultural land for biomass, resulting in a significant increase to 17.2 million hectares by 2050. This larger land area supports the extensive use of biomass for energy and materials, driven by a more aggressive transition to bio-based solutions and a reduction in petroleum use. Also in this case, marginal and abandoned agricultural land could be used, to avoid affecting existing agriculture production (which may lead to indirect land use changes elsewhere) and forested areas.

In the scenario where transport is fully electrified, the demand for agricultural land is slightly reduced compared to the EUBB_hightransport scenario, with the total area projected to be 16.6 million hectares by 2050. This reduction is due to the decreased reliance on biomass as a fuel source, reflecting the efficiency gains and reduced need for biomass crops associated with electrification.

Figure 43: Agriculture land demand under various scenarios, considering that marginal and abandoned agriculture land could be converted for biomass production.

Figure 44: Stock of forest under various scenarios, without considering the potential to use marginal and abandoned agriculture land, representing a worst-case scenario.

Germany’s agricultural stock is projected to increase from 16 million hectares under the BAU scenario to 17.2 million hectares in the EUBB_hightransport scenario by 2050, reflecting a net increase of 1.2 million hectares. This net increase represents the additional land required for biomass production. However, when considering the 0.81 million hectares of abandoned land and

3.72 million hectares of marginal lands, the total available land for biomass production amounts to 4.53 million hectares (Table 18).

Table 18: Land use forecast and marginal lands for Germany (SOURCE: (Elbersen, Eupan , Meijinger , & Mantel, 2025))

Country	Agriculture Stock in million ha			Land abandonment in 2050 in million ha	marginal land in million ha	total land available for biomass production	Ratio forecast land for biomass demand to total marginal land
	BAU - 2050	EUBB_hightransport	Net difference				
Germany	16	17.2	1.2	0.81	3.72	4.53	3.78

This availability ensures that the demand for biomass can be met sustainably, reducing the risk of deforestation and avoiding displacement of productive agricultural areas. With proper land-use planning and policies that prioritize the use of marginal and abandoned land, Germany can achieve its CBBE targets while safeguarding food security and environmental conservation. By utilizing this underutilized land, the country demonstrates a pathway for sustainable biomass expansion.

3.5.2 Italy

The textile industry in Italy in 2024 represents 1.32% of the real national GDP. The sector includes the production of raw materials, textiles, and finished garments, and is distinguished by its use of premium materials and advanced technology. As a global leader in fashion, Italy's textile industry is adapting to new challenges, including the shift towards more sustainable practices such as bio-based transition. The national scenario for Italy and the textile industry includes the switch to bio-based fabrics, but also transition to bio-based sources such as for power generation, more sustainable waste practices, and a transition to more renewable fuels viewed through a socio-economic lens.

In the BAU scenario, Italy's real GDP is projected to increase from 1.77 trillion EUR in 2024 to 2.32 trillion EUR by 2050. This growth reflects the anticipated trajectory of the economy under current policies and trends. Under the Bio-Transition scenario, Italy's GDP is forecasted to reach 2.326 trillion EUR by 2050, indicating a slight increase compared to the BAU scenario (Figure 45). Similarly, the Bio-Revolution scenario also projects a national GDP of 2.326 trillion EUR by 2050, showing no additional economic benefit over the Bio-Transition scenario. In contrast, the implementation of EU-wide bio-based policies (EUBB) combined with electrification results in a significant economic boost for Italy. By 2050, Italy's GDP is expected to increase by 11.2% compared to the BAU scenario, reaching approximately 2.581 trillion EUR. This substantial growth reflects the positive economic impacts of more aggressive EUBB and electrification policies on Italy's economy.

Figure 45: Italy National GDP under various scenarios

In the BAU scenario, Italy’s industry GDP is projected to grow from 670 billion EUR in 2024 to 876 billion EUR by 2050. Under the Bio-Transition scenario, industry GDP is expected to rise to 878.1 billion EUR by 2050. The Bio-Revolution scenario, which includes a higher ambition for the bio-based transition of the textile industry, forecasts an industry GDP of 878.4 billion EUR by 2050 (Figure 46).

The introduction of EUBB policies with electrification leads to a more substantial increase in industry GDP. By 2050, industry GDP is projected to reach approximately 969 billion EUR, representing a 10.5% increase compared to the BAU scenario.

These projections highlight a moderate growth trajectory under the BAU scenario. The Bio-Transition scenario offers a modest improvement, while the Bio-Revolution scenario, driven by the higher ambition of the textile industry, results in a slightly higher industry GDP. The most significant economic impact is observed under the EUBB scenario with electrification, which results in a substantial increase in industry GDP. This increase reflects the broader economic benefits of integrating EUBB policies and electrification, supporting a more robust and competitive industrial sector that can positively contribute both to the environment and the economy.

Figure 46: Italy National Industry GDP under various scenarios

The higher levels of economic production result in more employment as the industries grow and thus, employment levels grow. In the BAU scenario, industry employment in Italy is estimated to be approximately 9.8 million people in 2024, with a modest increase to 9.84 million by 2050 (Figure 47). This indicates a stable employment outlook under current industry practices. Additionally, the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show that total industry employment remains largely unchanged as the size of the textile industry does not largely impact the overall employment levels. However, the EU bio-based transition (EUBB) scenario presents a more optimistic picture, with industrial employment projected to be, on average, 3.46% higher than in the BAU EU scenario. This increase reflects the potential for bio-based technologies to create additional job opportunities and stimulate employment growth, suggesting that a transition towards bio-based industry could contribute positively to the labour market despite its minimal impact in other scenarios.

Figure 47: Italy industry employment levels under various scenarios

As the national scenario involves a transformation to renewable bio-based energy, the levels of employment within the power generation sector are heavily impacted under the EUBB scenarios. In the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, which assumes lower levels of electrification in the transport sector, employment within the power generation sector is expected to surge to 435,750 by 2050. This figure further increases to 452,750 in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, reflecting the substantial job creation potential linked to extensive electrification of transport. Conversely, if the transport sector undergoes significant electrification, the employment in power generation is projected to decrease slightly to 443,246 by 2050. This is in contrast to the BAU scenario where the power generation sector employs 104,157 people in 2024 and 181,771 by 2050 (Figure 48). The higher levels of investment and construction projects to transition to renewable energy, in addition to the higher levels of energy demand, require more workers. These workers actively contribute by constructing the new energy capacity, resulting in 100% share of power generation being from renewable sources by 2050 (Figure 49).

Figure 48: Italy's power generation employment levels under various scenarios

Figure 49: Italy's share of renewable power generation under various scenarios

The transition to renewables impacts the energy bill for Italy as renewable energy is cheaper for the country. Thus, in the BAU scenario, Italy's energy expenditure is projected to be €188 billion in 2024, with a gradual increase to €192 billion by 2050, reflecting a steady rise in energy costs. In both the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, the energy bill follows a similar trajectory, decreasing slightly to €192 billion by 2050 (Figure 50). However, the EU bio-based transition (EUBB) scenarios exhibit more pronounced variations. In the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, which assumes lower levels of transport electrification, the energy bill sees a notable reduction, dropping to €162 billion annually by 2050. This reduction is even more substantial in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, where extensive reductions in petroleum use lead to an energy bill of €154 billion by 2050. Interestingly, if the transport sector undergoes significant electrification, the energy bill increases compared to the high transport scenario, rising to €160 billion annually.

Figure 50: Italy's energy bill under various scenarios

Despite the transition towards renewable energy and bio-based materials, emissions from Italy's industrial sector remains high as in the BAU scenario, industrial emissions are projected to rise from 32 million tons per year in 2024 to 42 million tons per year by 2050, reflecting a steady increase aligned with higher industrial activity and energy consumption (Figure 51). Similarly, the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show minimal impact on industrial emissions, with levels remaining largely consistent with those in the BAU scenario. In contrast, the EUBB scenarios present a different outcome. Despite the shift towards bio-based technologies and renewable energy sources, industrial emissions are expected to increase due to elevated economic activity, reaching 47 million tons per year by 2050.

Figure 51: Italy's Industry emissions under various scenarios

While the adoption of renewable energy sources and bio-based technologies represent a crucial step towards reducing environmental impact, the data reveals that significant emissions will persist. For instance, despite substantial progress in integrating bio-based materials and renewable energy, industrial emissions in Italy are projected to increase under the EU bio-based transition scenarios due to heightened economic activity. This highlights a critical gap: while bio-based technologies contribute to sustainability; they do not fully address the complex challenge of reducing industrial emissions. Additionally, if the demand for biomass, and consequent demand for land is not handled properly it can lead to deforestation and exacerbate challenges for reaching net zero emissions.

Specifically, the land demand forecast from GEM, indicated that in the BAU scenario, the area of agricultural land in Italy is projected to decrease from 12.3 million hectares in 2024 to 11 million hectares by 2050, reflecting ongoing changes in land use patterns (Figure 52). In contrast, the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios anticipate an increase in agricultural land to 11.8 million hectares by 2050, driven by higher demand for biomass. This trend is even more pronounced in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, where the need for biomass leads to a substantial expansion of agricultural land to 13.4 million hectares by 2050. However, if the transport sector undergoes significant electrification, the demand for agricultural land is somewhat reduced, with the area required falling to 12.6 million hectares by 2050.

Figure 52: Italy's agricultural land demand under various scenarios, considering that marginal and abandoned agricultural land could be converted for biomass production.

Figure 53: Italy's stock of forest under various scenarios, without considering the potential to use marginal and abandoned agricultural land, representing a worst-case scenario.

This projected increase in agricultural land under the EUBB_hightransport scenario reflects a net additional requirement of 2.4 million hectares by 2050. Importantly, this demand for biomass does not necessarily imply a risk of deforestation or displacement of productive agricultural activities. Italy's land-use dynamics reveal significant opportunities to mitigate such risks by utilizing underutilized land resources. Specifically, 1.02 million hectares of abandoned land and 3.81 million hectares of marginal lands are available, creating a combined total of 4.83 million hectares of land that can be repurposed for biomass production (Table 19).

Table 19: Land use forecast and marginal land for Italy (SOURCE: (Elbersen, Eupan , Meijinger , & Mantel, 2025))

Country	Agriculture Stock in million ha			Land abandoned in 2050 in million ha	marginal land in million ha	total land available for biomass production	Ratio forecast to total marginal land
	BAU - 2050	EUBB_hightrans port	Net difference				
Italy	11	13.4	2.4	1.02	3.81	4.83	2.01

By leveraging these underutilized land resources, Italy can meet its biomass demand sustainably while safeguarding food security and protecting ecosystems. This approach highlights the critical role of strategic land-use planning and policy in achieving a balanced transition to renewable energy, demonstrating how increased biomass production can coexist with environmental conservation and agricultural resilience.

3.5.3 Netherlands

The Netherlands, a small, but economically boisterous nation, is the 10th largest producer of chemicals globally (Government of the Netherlands, 2024). Despite the large contribution to the global chemical industry, the national industry only makes up 1.47% of national real GDP. Yet, chemical production often uses poisonous or toxic materials, which means that they contribute an outsized portion of global pollution. Transitioning to bio-based material is crucial to boost economic output, and do so in a sustainable manner. In this section, the BAU, Bio-Transition, Bio-Revolution, EU-wide bio-based scenarios will be presented for the Netherlands.

In the BAU scenario, the Netherlands' total real GDP is projected to increase from €832 billion in 2024 to €1.26 trillion by 2050. Under the Bio-Transition scenario, the national GDP is anticipated to rise to €1.28 trillion by 2050 (Figure 54). The Bio-Revolution scenario predicts a slightly higher GDP of €1.284 trillion by 2050. However, the introduction of EU-wide bio-based policies combined with electrification is expected to have the most significant impact, boosting the Netherlands' GDP by 10.8% compared to the BAU scenario, reaching €1.4 trillion by 2050. This substantial increase underscores the potential economic benefits of implementing ambitious bio-based and electrification strategies.

Figure 54: The Netherlands national GDP under various scenarios

Disaggregating the national GDP, into the three economic sectors, we see the same trend emerge. As this is mainly concerned with the industry, only industrial GDP will be presented. In the BAU scenario, the GDP of the industrial sector in the Netherlands is projected to grow from €235 billion in 2024 to €335 billion by 2050 (Figure 55). Under the Bio-Transition scenario, this figure is expected to rise to €338 billion by 2050, driven by the increased adoption of bio-based materials. The Bio-Revolution scenario anticipates a slightly higher industrial GDP of €339 billion by 2050, reflecting the significantly higher ambition for the transition to bio-based materials in the chemical industry. However, if EU-wide bio-based policies are combined with electrification, the industrial sector’s GDP is projected to reach €370 billion by 2050, representing a 10.5% increase compared to the BAU scenario. This notable growth highlights the potential for substantial economic gains from integrating bio-based and electrification strategies within the industrial sector.

Figure 55: the Netherlands national Industry GDP under various scenarios

Interestingly, with the higher levels of economic output in the industrial sectors there is a decline in employment due to capital replacing labour. In the BAU scenario, total industry employment in the Netherlands is estimated to be 2.01 million people in 2024, decreasing to 1.8 million by 2050 (Figure 56). The Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show minimal impact on industry employment, with figures remaining largely consistent with the BAU scenario. However, under the EU bio-based transition (EUBB), industrial employment is anticipated to be, on average, 0.31% lower compared to the BAU scenario. This slight reduction reflects the complex interplay between the shift towards bio-based materials and the overall dynamics of the industrial labour market, indicating that while bio-based strategies may drive economic and environmental benefits, they do not substantially alter employment levels in the industrial sector.

Figure 56: The Netherlands industry employment levels under various scenarios

This is in contrast to the increasing levels of employment in the power generation sector due to the transition to bio-based renewable energy, simulating increased investments and construction in the sector. Thus, in the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, employment within the power generation sector in the Netherlands is projected to rise to 130,312 by 2050, driven by increased demand for bio-based energy sources (Figure 57). This figure sees a slight increase in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, reaching 131,200 by 2050, reflecting the additional employment opportunities created by extensive bio-based and renewable energy initiatives. However, if the transport industry undergoes significant electrification, the employment in power generation is expected to decrease to 130,628 by 2050. This is in contrast to the BAU scenario, where employment within the Netherlands' power generation sector increases from 33,169 in 2024 to 38,832 by 2050 due to rising energy demand.

Figure 57: The Netherlands power generation employment levels under various scenarios

The larger investments and higher levels of employment in the power generation sector reflect a significant shift in the share of renewable energy generation across various scenarios. In the BAU scenario, the proportion of power generation from renewable sources remains relatively constant at around 33% through to 2050, with investments and employment levels growing in response to increasing energy demand. In both the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, the share of renewable generation does not deviate from the BAU scenario, maintaining this steady proportion. However, the EUBB scenarios demonstrate a substantial increase in the share of renewable generation due to a strategic focus on biofuels, wind, and solar energy. By 2050, the share of power generation from renewable sources reaches 96% (Figure 58).

Figure 58: The Netherlands share of power generation from renewable sources under various scenarios

This results in an overall, lower energy bill compared to BAU, in the EUBB_lowtransport scenario, the annual costs decrease to €67 billion by 2050 (Figure 59). This reduction is further enhanced in the EUBB_hightransport scenario, where the energy bill falls to €66 billion by 2050 due to a substantial decrease in petroleum use and a greater emphasis on renewable energy sources. However, if the transport sector undergoes extensive electrification, the energy bill increases to €67 billion annually, surpassing the costs projected under the high transport scenario.

Figure 59: The Netherlands energy bill under various scenarios

Despite the significant shift towards renewable energy sources, the impact on national industrial emissions remains limited due to minimal investment in carbon capture and storage (CCS) and waste management policies. In the BAU scenario, emissions from industrial processes in the Netherlands are projected to rise from 8.6 million tons per year in 2024 to 12.2 million tons per year by 2050, reflecting ongoing industrial activity and energy demands (Figure 60). The Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios show little change in industrial emissions compared to the BAU scenario, indicating that renewable energy adoption alone does not substantially alter emission levels. In the EUBB scenarios, emissions are expected to increase further to 13.5 million tons per year by 2050, driven by higher economic activity and limited progress in emission reduction technologies.

Figure 60: The Netherlands national industry emissions under various scenarios

The bio-based transition, aimed at shifting from conventional materials to renewable and bio-based materials, results in a substantial increase in land demand due to the need for large-scale biomass production. As industries and energy systems increasingly adopt bio-based inputs—such as biofuels, bioplastics, and other renewable resources—the requirement for agricultural land to grow these biomass feedstocks rises sharply. This transition drives up the demand for land as more acreage is needed to cultivate crops and manage resources essential for bio-based production. In the Netherlands, agricultural land is expected to expand from 1.82 million hectares in 2024 to 2.14 million hectares by 2050 under the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenarios, reflecting the higher biomass demand (Figure 61). The EUBB_hightransport scenario further intensifies this trend, increasing agricultural land demand to 2.16 million hectares by 2050.

Figure 61: The Netherlands agriculture land demand under various scenarios, considering that marginal and abandoned agriculture land could be converted for biomass production.

This increased agricultural land use under the EUBB_hightransport scenario represents a modest net additional requirement of 0.03 million hectares by 2050. However, the Netherlands' limited land resources necessitate a careful approach to meet this increased demand. With 0.13 million hectares of abandoned land and 0.27 million hectares of marginal lands available, a total of 0.41 million hectares could potentially be repurposed for biomass production (Table 20).

Table 20: Land use and marginal land for the Netherlands (SOURCE: (Elbersen, Eupan , Meijinger , & Mantel, 2025))

Country	Agriculture Stock in million ha			Land abandonment in 2050 in million ha	marginal lands in million ha	total land available for biomass production	Ratio forecast to total marginal land
	BAU - 2050	EUBB_hightransport	Net difference				
Netherlands	2.13	2.16	0.03	0.13	0.27	0.41	13.53

This available land significantly exceeds the forecasted demand, indicating that the Netherlands can accommodate the bio-based transition without resorting to deforestation or compromising productive agricultural land. Strategic land-use planning, focusing on utilizing abandoned and marginal lands, is essential to ensure a sustainable and environmentally responsible transition to bio-based materials. The ratio of marginal land to the projected biomass demand further highlights the feasibility of this transition. Even though abandoned land is less productive than active agricultural land, it could still contribute significantly to biomass production. For instance, if abandoned land is 13.53 times less productive than marginal land, it would still be sufficient to meet the forecasted demand for biomass by 2050. This suggests that even with lower productivity rates, the available land—primarily marginal and abandoned—remains more than adequate to accommodate the bio-based transition, ensuring that the land use change is both sustainable and does not encroach upon vital agricultural areas.

4 DOCUMENTATION OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY MODEL

This model offers a comprehensive framework for analysing the materials lifecycle and energy dynamics within the construction sector. By initializing the model with the demand for housing, driven by population dynamics and per capita housing preferences, it accurately reflects the real-world scenario. The subsequent analysis of construction materials consumption, particularly cement, provides insights into resource utilization and potential areas for optimization.

Furthermore, the model's incorporation of lifecycle considerations, including reuse, recycling, and disposal of construction materials, adds depth to the analysis. By integrating considerations of policy-induced changes, the model can forecast employment generation within the construction industry, thereby providing stakeholders with valuable insights into the economic impacts of various policy interventions. Moreover, the model delves into the energy consumption dynamics inherent in the construction sector, shedding light on the sources and magnitudes of emissions associated with energy utilization. By dissecting energy consumption across various sources such as natural gas, oil, electricity, renewables, and biofuels, the model enables stakeholders to identify potential areas for mitigation strategies and transitions towards greener alternatives.

4.1 Demand & Housing Stock

The estimation of demand for housing is used to determine the amount of construction materials required based on the average m2 per person (see Figure 62). The demand serves as the primary driver in the model, providing input to the other components of the model. Without the need for housing, the energy, recycling, and employment structures would not only fail to increase but would instead diminish towards zero.

Figure 62: Cause tree Housing Demand

The demand for housing is driven exogenously by the average m2 per person, with the data specifically and the population forecasts for Germany (UN Population Division, 2022).

$$\text{desired building stock} = \text{users} * \text{average m2 per person}$$

The model uses a stock and flow structure, with the inflow representing construction and the outflow being the demolition of housing. The stock represents the number of buildings that are operational and in use. The desired building stock drives demand for buildings, which is calculated based on the desired building stock and the number of houses being commissioned, using a MAX function to prevent it from becoming negative.

$$\text{demand for buildings} = \max(0, \text{desired building stock} + \text{decommissioning})$$

The building stock increases through construction and decreases through decommissioning. The lifetime of buildings, which determines the decommissioning rate, is initially set to 35 years. This duration illustrates that despite buildings having longer lifetimes, certain aspects may require repair earlier. The following assumptions, presented in Table 21, are used to calculate demand and to check its validity. Among the policies or interventions considered in the model, one relates to the lifetime of buildings, which can be extended via retrofits. Hence, the policy being represented through extending the building lifetime.

Table 21: Parameters used in the demand model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Initial Lifetime	35	(Madhumitha, 2024)
Lifetime CBBE	Annual increase of 1.5%	Assumption
Average m2 per person	47	(Destatis, 2018)
m2 per dwelling	93	(Destatis, 2018)
Building Stock Value (2022)	43,336,000	(Destatis, 2022)

4.2 Material Consumption

Material consumption is estimated based on the construction rate. It reflects the amount of material that is required for new construction in any given year. The material consumed in prior construction can be recycled and reused, reducing the virgin materials used. In addition, if waste is generated during the construction process, some of the materials used will be stored in buildings, while others will be sent to landfill (if recycling is not possible) and disposed of.

The material consumption per sqm, labelled material consumption per unit in the model, decides the material consumed depending on scenarios. The equation thus, being:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{material consumption per unit} = \\ & \text{IF THEN ELSE}(\text{CEMENT TO WOOD switch}=1:\text{AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \\ & \text{material consumption per unit CBBE}(\text{Time}) * \text{material consumption cement to wood CBBE}, \\ & \text{IF THEN ELSE}(\text{CEMENT TO WOOD switch}=0:\text{AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \\ & \text{material consumption per unit CBBE}(\text{Time}), \\ & \text{IF THEN ELSE}(\text{CEMENT TO WOOD switch}=1:\text{AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=0, \\ & \text{material consumption per unit BAU} * \text{material consumption cement to wood CBBE}, \\ & \text{material consumption per unit BAU})) \end{aligned}$$

The IF THEN ELSE statement dictates, depending on which switch is active, the material consumption. If the “cement to wood switch” and the “material efficiency switch” are turned on (=1), the model will be impacted by various policy interventions. When the former switch is activated, cement demand will decline, and more wood will be consumed. If the latter switch is activated cement will still be used, but in lower quantity. The logic allows for the interventions to be combined, thus, creating 4 possible scenarios, including the business-as-usual. The variable values and sources used in the material consumption per unit are shown in Table 22.

Table 22: Parameters used in the material consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
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Material Consumption per unit BAU	1.91	(Karina & Annette, 2022)
Material Consumption per unit CBBE	A 1.5% annual increase in efficiency	Scenario
Material Consumption per unit cement to wood CBBE	0.5	

Recycled or reused materials are fed back into the material consumption process, reducing the demand for virgin materials. However, a minimum value of 0.1 is set for this variable to prevent it from becoming zero or negative. This reflects the fact that the model only considers virgin materials.

$$\text{Material consumption} = \max(0.1, \text{construction} * \text{material consumption per unit-products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse-delay material recycling and reuse-domestic reuse of construction materials})$$

The production waste from the construction of the buildings can be reused in later developments (Osmani, 2011). The equation for material recycling and reuse thus accounts for the percentage of waste able to be used and the amount of waste from that percentage that is actually reused.

$$\text{Material recycling and reuse} = \text{"end of life materials (waste)" * IF THEN ELSE(MATERIAL RECYCLING AND REUSE switch=0, share of material recycling and reuse BAU, share of material recycling and reuse(Time))}$$

The equation represents the management of recycling and reuse within an industrial context. It assesses the proportion of materials recycled or reused based on specific conditions. The "IF THEN ELSE" statement evaluates whether material recycling and reuse are active (represented by the "MATERIAL RECYCLING AND REUSE switch"). If the switch is set to zero, the model assumes a baseline scenario (BAU) and uses the predetermined share of recycling and reuse. Otherwise, it considers the increased share of production material to be reused. The assumptions and sources are presented in Table 23.

Table 23: Parameters used in the material recycling model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of material that is waste	30%	(Osmani, 2011)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	48%	(Osmani, 2011)
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	The materials that go to waste in the construction process are materials that are not easily recyclable. Hence, the policy would slowly increase by 0.05% annually. Reaching 70% by 2100.	

4.3 Recycling and Reusing

Decommissioning and construction activities influence the recycling infrastructure within the model by contributing to waste streams. This waste is collected and diverted for either landfilling, recycling, or reuse. Consequently, these activities increase the inflow of materials into the recycling system's stockpiles. Table 24 shows the inflows and outflows for each stock modelled in this section.

Table 24: Overview of stocks and flows for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Product waste generated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste generated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected
Product waste collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse Products materials to landfill Products resold and reused
Landfill material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product materials to landfill Production materials to landfill 	None

As more buildings are decommissioned, the stock of product waste generated increases, which in turn increases the stock of product waste collected. The stock of product waste collected is then decreased through three outflows that either dismantle the recycling materials, send them into the stock of landfill, or become resold. The material that is sent out from the recycling and reusing flows goes back to the material consumption equations to reduce the use of virgin materials. An overview of the structure can be found in Figure 63.

Figure 63: Stock and Flow Diagram for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Lastly, the variables that decide the share of materials being recycled, etc. are presented in Table 25 with their sources and values. Alongside them are also their policy scenario counterparts to demonstrate the decided upon aspirations. The BAU and CBBE scenarios can be individually controlled for greater exploration of the possible simulation space in the model.

Table 25: Parameters used for the recycling model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	70%	(BMUV, ND)
Share of products collected CBBE	A 1.5% annual increase	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	68% in 2012	(Deloitte, 2015)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	A 2.8% annual increase since 2022	(European Environment Agency, 2022b)
Fraction resold and reused BAU	Landfill and recycling compose 72% of Construction and demolition waste, we are therefore assuming the rest is resold or reused.	(Deloitte, 2015)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	In the CBBE scenario, the recycling rate increases till 90%, leaving 10% to either be resold or to be landfilled. The assumption is that half of it always goes to landfill.	

4.4 Employment

The employment sector calculates the level of employment under each task using an exogenous “person per product” formulation. This formulation means that if the scenarios increase the recycling or building flows, the employment is endogenously calculated. An example of the equation is as follows:

$$\text{Employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

The more products that are resold and reused, the larger the total employment for product repair and reuse is. Table 26 presents the values and sources for the employment equations. The units are person per product.

Table 26: Parameters used for the employment model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per m2	0.2	Calculated
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	X	
Employment per unit collected and sorted	X	
Employment per unit recycled	X	
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused	x	
Employment per unit of waste landfilled	x	
Employment per unit of water consumed	x	
Employment per unit of energy consumed	x	

4.5 Energy Consumption

The industry requires energy to run the tools and machines, and for materials to be consumed. In the model, energy consumption is determined by energy intensities and material consumption. Higher material consumption correlates with increased energy consumption, dependent on the constant energy intensity per source. Total fuel consumption is the sum of all energy consumed in TJ.

$$\text{total fuel consumption} = \text{renewables and biofuel consumption} + \text{oil and petroleum consumption} + \text{natural gas consumption} + \text{electricity consumption in TJ}$$

Using the energy consumption per type of energy, and the corresponding emission factor, determines the total CO₂e emission in tons for the industry.

$$\text{total CO2e emissions in tons} = \frac{(\text{fuel renewable and biofuel emissions} + \text{fuel electricity emissions} + \text{fuel oil and petroleum emissions} + \text{fuel natural gas emissions})}{\text{kg to ton}}$$

The energy intensities presented in Table 27 were calculated using the data for the total m2 constructed in 2022 and the associated energy consumption.

Table 27: Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.000244684 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	4.65907e-005 gWh/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum Intensity	0.000543392 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Renewables and Biofuel Intensity	2.45456e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

4.6 Energy Prices

The associated costs of energy in the industry are a detriment to sustainable transitions with the higher prices for renewables. To inform the cost-benefit analysis of the scenarios, the price of energy is used to see the various annual costs associated with any policy decisions. The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price from the data that is closest to 2022. The value and source can be found in Table 28.

Table 28: Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	9.71809e-005 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	0.1512 Euro/kWh	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Oil and Petroleum Price	32.5461 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Renewables and Biofuel Price	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(Statista Research Department, 2024)

4.7 Material Costs

One of the methods of reducing emissions and increasing the circularity of an industry is to shift towards more sustainable materials. In the construction sector, this could be a shift towards wood instead of cement. These different materials have different costs and thus, the model accounts for the shift. Table 29 displays the source and value of said costs per sqm of construction.

Table 29: Material costs used in the construction industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Costs per sqm in Cement Scenario	X	
Costs per sqm in Wood Scenario	X	

4.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of new construction and value addition per m2. Two variations of the value addition per m2 are calculated, one for conventional construction and one for bio-based construction. The module only considers the value addition from new construction, and not secondary markets, such as real estate or market speculation.

Figure 64: Cause tree for Value addition in the construction sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Destatis, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$Value\ addition\ intensity = \frac{Value\ addition_t}{Production_t}$$

The forecast for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the construction value addition, this 0.66% growth annually. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top from literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023;

Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature has ranged from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future bio-based value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Germany, and thus, the construction sectors, the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 2.6% (see Figure 65).

Figure 65: Value addition conventional and bio-based for Germany's construction industry

The value addition or construction GDP is then the sum of the value addition, new construction, and share of the industry that is bio-based, which is dependent on the policy levers active during the simulation. Taking the share of new production that is bio-based and the counterfactual gives a value addition that accounts for both. The equation is the sum of new construction and conventional value addition, accounting for the share that is bio-based added to the share of construction value addition that is bio-based.

$$\text{Real value added new purchases construction industry} = \\
 ((\text{construction} * \text{value added per virgin product construction} * (1 - \text{share of construction products manufactured using bio-based products})) + (\text{construction} * \text{value added per virgin bio-based material construction} * (\text{share of construction products manufactured using bio-based products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}$$

Since the construction GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real construction GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 66: Use tree for real GDP construction industry

5 DOCUMENTATION OF THE PLASTIC INDUSTRY MODEL

This model is a comprehensive framework for analysing the lifecycle of materials in the plastics sector in Germany. It starts with the initialization of demand based on per capita plastic usage and total population figures, providing a realistic picture of the demand for plastic products. The model gives insights into the materials consumption dynamics within the industry.

Moreover, the model offers a lifecycle analysis that covers the reuse, recycling, and disposal of plastic products, providing a nuanced understanding of resource utilization and waste management practices. The model also takes into account employment generation within the plastics industry and the potential impacts of policy interventions such as measures to promote recycling or reduce single-use plastics. This allows stakeholders to evaluate the socio-economic implications of different strategies. Additionally, the model considers the energy consumption and CO2 emissions associated with the plastics industry, categorized by sources such as natural gas, heat, and electricity. This provides valuable insights into the environmental footprint of plastic production processes.

5.1 Plastic Demand

The demand for plastic is driven by consumption and thus, the two can be equated. To calculate demand in the model a static value for plastic consumption per capita is used and multiplied with the data and population forecast for Germany (UN Population Division, 2022). This provides a simple forecast of plastic demand in the future. In the BAU scenario, the plastic consumption per capita is set to 160kg derived from tons of plastic produced and the German population (Görlitz, 2018).

$$\text{Plastic consumption} = \text{users} * \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{REDUCTION PC USE switch} = 0, \text{plastic consumption per capita BAU}, \text{plastic consumption per capita (Time)})$$

The logic statement allows for policy scenarios to be run with different plastic consumption per capita. In this case, it represents a ban on certain plastic packaging causing a reduction in plastic consumption. The policy values can be found in Table 22.

Plastic consumption drives the demand for the industry, which affects the stock of product in use. The stock increases through the product purchase and decreases through product discard. The stock represents all plastic and does not disaggregate between the different products. The outflow is determined by an adjustment time set as 10 years in the BAU scenario, and the CBBE scenario is a table function.

$$\text{product discard} = \frac{\text{Product stock in use}}{\text{product lifetime}}$$

The values and sources for the policy for plastic consumption and products in use can be seen in Table 30.

Table 30: Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Plastic Consumption per capita BAU	0.16	(Görlitz, 2018)
Plastic Consumption per capita CBBE	2023= 0.16; 2030= 0.12; 2050= 0.4	
Initial product lifetime	10	(Madhumitha, 2024)
Product lifetime scenario	2023= 10; 2030= 20	

5.2 Material Consumption

Material consumption is the amount of material consumed during the production of a plastic product. In the model, material consumption is driven by purchases to determine the number of materials needed, the recycled waste from previous productions, and recycled materials from discarded products. Recycled plastics reduce material consumption as they are not new in the system, hence the subtraction of recycled materials. The variable material consumption is only concerned with virgin plastics.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit-products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} - \text{delay material recycling and reuse}$$

Material consumption refers to the overall utilization of materials within the system, encompassing both the acquisition of new materials and the reuse of existing ones. This is calculated by multiplying the quantity of products purchased by the amount of material consumed per unit of product, and then subtracting the materials recycled and reused. Some of the material that is consumed during production can be recycled which is determined by the following equation:

$$\text{material recycling and reuse} = \text{"end of life materials (waste)" * IF THEN ELSE(PRODUCTION MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=0, share of material recycling and reuse BAU, share of material recycling and reuse(Time))}$$

The equation considers both the share of material designated as waste and the proportion of material suitable for recycling to determine the materials available for reuse within the system. The switch enables toggling between the BAU scenario and the policy scenario.

To calculate the material consumed per unit the model uses an exogenous material consumption per unit variable that determines how many tons of input materials are needed for one ton of plastic products.

$$\text{material consumption per unit} = \text{IF THEN ELSE("BIO-BASED PLASTICS switch"}=1 \text{ :AND: MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \text{ bio-based material consumption per unit CBBE} * \text{material efficiency increase CBBE, IF THEN ELSE("BIO-BASED PLASTICS switch"}=1, \text{ bio-based material consumption per unit CBBE, IF THEN ELSE(MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \text{ material consumption per unit BAU} * \text{material efficiency increase CBBE, material consumption per unit BAU))}$$

The logic statement is designed to facilitate multiple policy tests, including overlapping policies such as increasing material efficiency and introducing bio-based plastics. These policies are aimed at reducing material consumption, emissions, and waste concurrently. The values of the parameters and sources can be found in Table 31.

Table 31: Parameters used for the material consumption model component, plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of Material that is waste	50%	(Gravgård, Kristensen, Svantesson, & Urhammer, 2021)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	9%	(United Nations Development Programme, 2023)
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=9%; 2030=11%; 2050=15%	

Material Consumption per Unit BAU	1.4 tons/product	
Bio-based material consumption per unit CBBE	1	
Material efficiency increase CBBE	1	
Product lifetime scenario	Baseline: 10 Policy: Increases to 20 by 2030	

5.3 Recycling and Reuse

The waste generated during production and discarded plastic products in Germany is collected by waste collectors and subsequently sorted into recycling, reuse, and landfill categories. The model structure mirrors this behaviour, as waste from production and any product in use eventually enters the waste management system. Table 32 presents a summary of the three stocks used in this section and its respective inflows and outflows.

Table 32: Overview of stocks and flows for recycling model component, plastics industry model

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Product waste generated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste generated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected
Product waste collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product waste collected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products dismantled for materials recycled and reused Products materials to landfill Products resold and reused
Landfill material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product materials to landfill Production materials to landfill 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials to incineration

Initially, the discarded products enter the stock of product waste generated where it is then transferred to the stock of product waste collected determined by the share of products collected (see Table 33). From the stock of product waste collected, there are three possible paths: reuse and resold, recycling, and landfill. If the plastic ends up in landfill, there is a possibility it is incinerated.

The flows are dictated by the recycling and reusing rates, with the remaining plastics that are not reused or recycled being directed to the landfill. To determine the landfill rate, the equation accounts for the inflow and then subtracts the sum of the other two outflows. This means that if there is a 100% recycling and reusing rate, there should be no materials flowing into the landfill stock. The materials that are recycled and reused flow back into the material consumption and plastic demand respectively.

$$\text{materials (products) landfilled} = \text{product waste collection} - (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} + \text{products resold and reused})$$

The recycling, reusing, incineration, and collection rates are determined by data and the policy scenarios are based on country aspirations. The value for which can be found in Table 33.

Table 33: Parameters used for the material recycling and reuse model component, the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	73%	(European Environment Agency, 2022a)
Share of products collected CBBE	2023=73%; 2030=80%; 2050=90%	
Fraction resold and reused BAU	11%	(Herrmann, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	30% of plastics that is not recycled in CBBE scenario	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	55%	(Eurostat, 2023a)
Share of materials to incineration	50%	(Herrmann, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)
Fraction of sorted plastic sold domestically BAU	5%	(Herrmann, Kast, Kuehl, Philipp, & Stuchtey, 2021)
Fraction of sorted plastic sold domestically CBBE	2023=5%; 2030=10%; 2050=20%	

5.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The model tracks downstream employment, such as the employment per recycling material, etc. One example of the equations is as follows:

$$\text{Employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{Employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This equation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton. While the model is not parametrized, the model is set up to accommodate the use of additional inputs, as shown in Table 34.

Table 34: Parameters used for the employment model component, the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	Not parametrized	
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused		
Employment per unit collected and sorted		
Employment per unit recycled		
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused		
Employment per unit of waste landfilled		
Employment per unit of water consumed		
Employment per unit of energy consumed		
Employment per unit of waste incinerated		

The tree diagram presented in Figure 67 shows the different sources of employment in the plastics industry, but also in all the industries (construction, chemicals, and textiles).

Figure 67: Sources of employment in the plastics industry

5.5 Energy Consumption

The plastic industry's main share of power comes from electricity, natural gas, heat, and other energy sources (Destatis, 2017). Using calculated energy intensities, the model converts the material consumption into energy consumption to endogenously calculate the emission from the industry. Figure 68 shows the cause tree for the electricity formulation, as all other equations follow the same structure.

Figure 68: Causes tree for electricity emissions from plastic production, the plastics industry model

The sum of the emissions is used to calculate the total CO₂e emissions from the German plastic industry. Regarding fuel costs, the equation takes the 2022 price of electricity in the country and multiplies it by the energy consumption to find the annual energy cost. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment.

The energy intensities were calculated by dividing the annual energy consumption, in TJ, with the tons produced given the following values in TJ/ton except for the electricity intensity which is in kWh/ton (see Table 35).

Table 35: Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.002145	(Destatis, 2017)
Heat Intensity	0.000331154	(Destatis, 2017)
Electricity Intensity	1100.09	(Destatis, 2017)
Other Energy Source	0.000208769	(Destatis, 2017)

5.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in Table 36. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating, the same values are used for both prices.

Table 36: Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	0.0269947 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	0.1513 Euro/kWh	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Heat Price	1.3176e-006 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Other Energy Sources	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(Statista Research Department, 2024)

5.7 Material Costs

One policy aimed at reducing plastic usage involves transitioning to bio-based plastics to enhance the industry's sustainability. However, producing bio-based plastics incurs distinct costs, particularly when examined at an aggregate level. In other words, categorizing all plastics as "plastic products" does not accurately reflect the varied costs associated with producing bio-based plastics. The price per ton of plastics is detailed in Table 37. The costs are measured in euro/ton.

Table 37: Material costs used in the plastics industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Costs per ton of plastic	1000	(CAP ECO Recycling, ND)

5.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of new plastic purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for bio-based production. The module only considers the value addition from purchases, including reused plastics.

Figure 69: Cause tree for Value addition in the plastic sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Görlitz, 2018; UN Population Division, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$Value\ addition\ intensity = \frac{Value\ addition_t}{Production_t}$$

The forecast for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the plastics value addition, this 0.66% growth annually. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top from literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature has ranged from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence,

each country has its future bio-based value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Germany, and thus, the plastics sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 2.6% (see Figure 70).

Figure 70: Value addition conventional and bio-based for Germany's plastic industry

The GDP of the plastics industry is calculated by summing the value addition, plastic purchases, and the bio-based share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the bio-based value addition, we consider the share of new production that is bio-based along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both bio-based and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of plastic purchases, conventional value addition, and the bio-based shares of both plastic purchases and bio-based value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of bio-based and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{real value added new purchases plastics industry=} \\
 & ((\text{product purchase} \times \text{value added per virgin product} \times (1 - \text{share of plastics products manufactured using bio-} \\
 & \text{based products})) + (\text{product purchase} \times \text{value added per virgin bio-based material} \times (\text{share of plastics products} \\
 & \text{manufactured using bio-based products} \quad))) \times \text{COVID shock on capital}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the plastics GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real plastic GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 71: Use tree for real GDP plastic industry

6 DOCUMENTATION OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY MODEL

This model offers a comprehensive analysis of the life cycle of materials used in the textile sector in Italy. It begins by calculating the demand for textiles based on the per capita consumption and total population of the country. This allows for a precise understanding of the dynamics of material consumption in the industry, with a particular focus on textile fibres as the primary component.

The model also incorporates a life cycle analysis that covers the use and disposal of textile fibres, reflecting a circular approach that promotes sustainability and resource efficiency. It takes into account the employment generated within the textile industry and the potential impacts of policy interventions, such as measures to promote textile recycling or reduce textile waste. This enables stakeholders to evaluate the socio-economic implications of different strategies.

Furthermore, the model also considers the energy consumption and CO2 emissions associated with textile production processes, categorized by sources such as natural gas, oil and petroleum, renewables, heat, and electricity. This provides valuable insights into the environmental footprint of the industry.

6.1 Textile Demand

The Italian textile sector is a major industry in the country and reached 8 billion euros in sales in 2022 (Industria Italiana, 2023). The per capita consumption was calculated based on total sales in euros divided by price in euros to get the kilograms of textile produced. This is then divided by the population of Italy to get the ton/person value for per capita consumption (see Table 38). The consumption for Italian textiles is then calculated using data and a population forecast for Italy and the per capita consumption (UN Population Division, 2022). To find the consumption of new textiles, the following equation is used:

$$\text{consumption of new textiles} = \max(0, \text{textile consumption} - \text{reuse of textile in products}) / \text{relative product lifetime}$$

The subtraction of reused textiles is performed to avoid double-counting in the product purchase flow. Consequently, the variable only addresses new textiles, ensuring that the inflow to the stock of product stock in use includes reintroduced reused textiles back into circulation.

$$\text{product purchase} = \max(0, (\text{consumption of new textiles} + \text{reuse of textile in products}))$$

The stock of “product stock in use” represents the ton of textiles being used within Italy over time. It increases through inflow, product purchase and decreases through the outflow, product discard. The product discard is the stock divided by the adjustment time, which can be altered depending on the scenario currently being simulated.

Table 38: Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Sales in 2022	8,100,000,000 Euro	(Industria Italiana, 2023)
KG price	0.57 Euro/kg	(European Environment Agency, 2023)
Product Lifetime BAU	3.6 Years	(Manshoven, et al., 2019)
Product Lifetime CBBE	2023=3.6; 2030=4.6; 2050=5	

6.2 Material Consumption

To produce textiles, raw materials such as fibre, cotton, and water are used. The material consumption in the model is calculated using the product purchases as a proxy for production, material consumption per unit, and accounts for recycled materials.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit-products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse-delay material recycling and reuse}$$

This equation calculates the total consumption of virgin materials. It multiplies "product purchase" by "material consumption per unit." Recycled materials are excluded here because their environmental impact, including energy costs, has already been accounted for elsewhere in the model.

The recycled materials come from prior textile production waste that can be reused. The material consumption per unit is based on the exogenous input, "material consumption per unit" which is measured in tons of materials consumed per ton of material produced.

$$\text{material consumption per unit} = \text{IF THEN ELSE (MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch=1, material consumption per unit CBBE (Time), material consumption per unit BAU)}$$

The larger the material consumption per unit is, the more materials will be needed to produce the same amount of textile. Thus, the higher the material consumption per unit, the lower the material efficiency is. This variable also determines the water and energy consumed from the production process. The parameters and their sources are provided in Table 39.

Table 39: Parameters used for the material consumption model component, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of Material that is waste	11%	(Consorto italiano Implementazione Detox, 2022)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	46%	(Consorto italiano Implementazione Detox, 2022)
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=46%; 2030=60%; 2050=80%	
Material Consumption per Unit BAU	1	
bio-based material consumption per unit CBBE	2023= 1; 2030= 1; 2050= 1	
Water Consumption per Unit	352.113 Litre/Ton	
Energy Consumption per Unit	0.00287732 TJ/ton	Calculated

Energy Carbon Intensity	26.2 TonCO ₂ e/TJ	(Normand, 2023)
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6.3 Recycling and Reuse

After textiles have been used on average for 3.6 years, the model routes the products into the recycling structure. This structure calculates waste generated and waste collected, determining the subsequent destination for the waste, the options being reused as is, recycled into fibres, or landfilled. The material flow is determined by rates that control the in and outflows of the structure, and the values under scenarios can be seen in Table 40.

The “products resold and reused” outflow drives the domestic reuse of textiles as the percentage that is resold domestically is sent back to product purchases. The products that are dismantled reduce the material consumption since the fibres do not need to be reproduced. Lastly, the materials that are landfilled are either sent to be incinerated or left in landfills. The stock of landfill is also affected by production waste. Since only a small part of landfills are ever properly disposed of, the share of materials that are incinerated remains low.

The rates for the in and out-flows were determined through the use of national level data or proxies when such data was not available. Table 40 shows the values of the parameters and their source.

Table 40: Recycling, Reusing, and Landfill Rates for Italy, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	10%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Share of products collected CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=50%;2050=100%	
Fraction resold and reused BAU	5%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=45%;2050=100%	
Fraction of sorted textiles sold domestically BAU	40%	(Janmark, Magnus, Strand, Langguth, & Hedrich, 2022)
Fraction of sorted textiles sold domestically CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=45%;2050=55%	

Fraction recycled and reused BAU	10%	(Textile Insights, 2023)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=20%;2050=50%	
Share of Materials to incineration	80%	(Graham, 2020)

6.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the downstream level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The equations are as follows:

$$\text{employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This equation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton. While the model is not parametrized, the model is set up to accommodate the use of additional inputs, as shown in Table 41.

Table 41: Parameters used for the employment model component, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	Not parametrized	
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused		
Employment per unit collected and sorted		
Employment per unit recycled		
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused		
Employment per unit of waste landfilled		

Employment per unit of water consumed		
Employment per unit of energy consumed		
Employment per unit of waste incinerated		

6.5 Energy Consumption

The Italian textile industry is powered by a variety of different energy sources. The model structure calculates energy consumption per source using the associated energy intensities from the year 2022. The structure proceeds to use the energy consumption with the associated emission factor to calculate the emissions per source (see Figure 72).

Figure 72: Causes tree for total CO2 emissions from textile production, the textile industry model

The sum of the emissions is then used to calculate the total CO2e emissions from the textile industry. Regarding fuel costs, the equation takes the 2022 price of energy in the country and multiplies it by the energy consumption to find the annual energy cost. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment.

The energy intensities were produced by dividing the ton of textile produced in 2022 by energy consumption per energy source in the same year. The energy intensities can be found in Table 42.

Table 42: Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
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Natural Gas Intensity	0.00150493 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Heat Intensity	1.5e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	0.000344084 GWH/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum	9.60563e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Renewables Intensity	2.26761e-005 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

6.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price with the data selected as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in Table 43. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating, the same values are used for both prices. Italy's renewable energy primarily comes from solar and hydro sources, predominantly utilized for electricity production. Consequently, the prices for both sources are generally the same.

Table 43: Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	3.1752e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023c)
Electricity Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Heat Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)
Oil and Petroleum Price	6.74535 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Renewable Energy Price	7.3116e-007 Euro/TJ	(Eurostat, 2023d)

6.7 Material Costs

The costs of materials are contingent upon the input materials utilized. Given that the model assesses the textile industry at an aggregate level, the cost of materials is averaged to euros per ton of textile produced. However, the cost of materials would vary if the policy's share of recycled

fibres increased. The following equation was utilized to compute the cost of materials, considering the proportion of recycled fibres used.

$$\text{Annual Industry Cost for Materials} = (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} * \text{Cost of Recycled Fibers}) + (\text{Cost of Input Materials} * \text{material consumption})$$

The parameters used for the equation can be found in Table 44.

Table 44: Material costs used in the textile industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Cost of Recycled Fibers	Not parametrized	
Cost of Input Materials	Not parametrized	

6.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of textile purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for bio-based production. The module considers the value addition from purchases, including reused textile, but does not disaggregate between the two.

Figure 73: Cause tree for Value addition in the textile sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (Industria Italiana, 2023; European Environment Agency, 2023; Manshoven, et al., 2019) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$\text{Value addition intensity} = \frac{\text{Value addition}_t}{\text{Production}_t}$$

The forecast for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the textile value addition, this 0.83% growth annually from 2028 onwards. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional

percentage increase on top from literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future bio-based value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of Italy, and thus, the textile sectors' additional value addition was calibrated to 5% (see Figure 74).

Figure 74: Value addition, conventional and bio-based for Italy's textile industry

The GDP of the textile industry is calculated by summing the value addition, new purchases, and the bio-based share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the bio-based value addition, we consider the share of new production that is bio-based along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both bio-based and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of textile purchases, conventional value addition, and the bio-based shares of both textile purchases and value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of bio-based and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\text{real value added new purchases textile industry} = \frac{((\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin product} * (1 - \text{share of textile products manufactured using bio-based products})) + (\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin bio-based material} * (\text{share of textile products manufactured using bio-based products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}}{1}$$

Since the textile GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real textile GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 75: Use tree for real GDP textile industry

7 DOCUMENTATION OF THE CHEMICALS INDUSTRY MODEL

The chemicals industry model for the Netherlands offers a comprehensive analysis of the intricate nexus between population dynamics, chemicals demand, materials lifecycle, energy consumption, and CO2 emissions within the chemicals sector. The model starts by analysing the chemicals demand per capita and the total population of the country, and then assesses material consumption patterns focusing on chemicals as raw materials. The model promotes a circular approach that includes stages such as use, reuse, recycling, and disposal, providing valuable insights into sustainable resource utilization practices within the chemicals industry. This approach supports the overarching goal of fostering a circular economy. The model also considers employment generation within the chemicals industry itself and as a result of policy interventions, offering a holistic perspective on the economic impacts of various strategies and initiatives.

Furthermore, the model addresses energy consumption and CO2 emissions associated with the chemicals industry from various sources such as natural gas, oil, waste, heat, and electricity. This provides a nuanced understanding of the environmental footprint of the sector and guides efforts towards emission reduction and the adoption of cleaner energy sources in alignment with the Netherlands' sustainability goals.

7.1 Chemical Demand

Chemical production predominantly serves the business-to-business (B2B) sector, emphasizing industrial demand. Consequently, the utilization of per capita consumption may introduce inaccuracies in the model. However, it serves as a useful proxy to align total production with demand due to the limited availability of data regarding industrial demand. The chemical consumption equation is thus derived from the UN data and population forecast for the Netherlands and a calculated per capita consumption (UN Population Division, 2022).

$$\text{chemicals consumption} = \text{users} * \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{CONSUMPTION switch}=0, \text{chemicals consumption per capita BAU}, \text{chemicals consumption per capita CBBE}(\text{Time}))$$

The logic statement allows for policy interventions between the normal per capita consumption and the CBBE scenario where industrial use of chemicals is reduced in favour of more sustainable options.

The product purchase represents the total purchasing of chemicals in the Netherlands and serves as a proxy for production. It is calculated with the consumption of new chemicals (derived from per capita consumption) and the share of chemicals being reused domestically.

$$\text{product purchase} = \text{max}(0, (\text{consumption of new chemicals} + \text{reuse of chemicals}))$$

The product purchase inflow increases the stock of products in use, which is decreased by the outflow of product discard. The outflow is determined by an adjustment time representing the average lifetime of a chemical product. The lifetime of chemicals can vary from months to decades and thus, a compromise is to use the shelf life of reagents (ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020). The parameters used in the demand structure can be found in Table 45.

Table 45: Parameters used for the demand and product use model components, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Per capita consumption BAU	1.72 ton/person	(cefic, 2023) & (Eurostat, 2023b)
Per capita consumption CBBE	2023=1.72; 2030=1.65; 2050=1.5	
Product lifetime BAU	1.7 Years	(ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020)
Product lifetime CBBE	2023=1.7; 2030=2; 2050: 5	

7.2 Material Consumption

The input in the chemical production process are reactants and initial materials that start a chemical reaction to produce the desired chemical. The variation in material efficiency based on which chemicals are being produced introduced complexities with working on an aggregate level. Hence, the parameters are calibrated with the most common chemical in mind, sulfuric acid. The values for all parameters can be found in Table 46.

With material consumption based on sulfuric acid, the equation for the variable is determined by a ton of input materials to produce a ton of chemicals. Under the CBBE scenario, the material efficiency is increased due to a transition to less biomass consumption.

$$\text{Material consumption per unit} = \text{IF THEN ELSE}(\text{MATERIAL EFFICIENCY switch}=1, \text{material consumption per unit CBBE}(\text{Time}) * \text{material consumption per unit BAU}, \text{material consumption per unit BAU})$$

The material consumption requires energy and water to be produced, which is determined by the energy and water consumption per unit (see Table 46). The shift from carbon intensive fuels to more renewable sources for direct energy use would reduce the carbon intensity from production (see Figure 76).

Figure 76: Cause tree for CO2e Emissions from Direct Energy Use, chemical industry model

Total material consumption is calculated using the material consumption per unit, product purchase and any recycled materials from the production or end of life processes.

$$\text{material consumption} = \text{product purchase} * \text{material consumption per unit} - \text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} - \text{delay material recycling and reuse}$$

The product purchase, as a proxy for production, and the material consumption per unit finds the total consumption of virgin materials. However, not all materials used in the process are new and thus, the recycled materials are subtracted from the total as they are already factored in for previous years.

Table 46: Parameters used for the material consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Material consumption per unit BAU	1.04 ton/product	(Cheremisinoff, 1995)
Material consumption per unit CBBE	2023=100%; 2030=30%,2050=40% efficiency increase	
Energy consumption per unit BAU	0.00018 TJ/ton	(umweltbundesamt, 2017)
Energy Consumption per unit CBBE	2023=0.00018; 2030=0.00015; 2050=0.00013	
Energy carbon intensity BAU	8.25e-011 tonco2e/TJ	(Innovation Fund, 2021)
Energy carbon intensity CBBE	2023=8.25e-011; 2030=8.25e-011;2050=8.25e-011	
Share of materials that is waste	75%	(wbcscd chemicals, 2015)
Share of material recycling and reuse BAU	10%	
Share of material recycling and reuse CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=30%; 2050=50%	

7.3 Recycling and Reuse

Chemical waste and disposed chemical products are directed into the waste and recycling structure, which determines the waste's destination—whether it is reused, recycled, or sent to landfill. Material flows within this structure are governed by rates controlling the inflows and outflows with values under different scenarios outlined in Table 39.

The flow of “products resold and reused” drives domestic reuse, as the percentage resold domestically is reintroduced into product purchases. Products that are dismantled contribute to reduced material consumption, as the chemical reactants can be reused. Finally, materials destined for landfill are either incinerated or left in landfills. The stock of landfill is also impacted by production waste.

The equation calculates the quantity of materials or products that end up in landfills by subtracting the diverted materials from the total waste collected. This includes both the products dismantled for recycling and reuse, as well as those resold and reused without dismantling. The equation quantifies the effectiveness of waste diversion efforts within the system, providing insights into the proportion of materials that are successfully diverted from landfills through recycling, reuse, or resale initiatives. There is a MAX function in the landfill outflow to negate the possibility of it becoming negative and thus, reverting direction.

$$\text{materials (products) landfilled} = \text{product waste collection} - (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} + \text{products resold and reused})$$

The values for the parameters used to calibrate the waste structure can be found in Table 47.

Table 47: Parameters used for the recycling model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Share of products collected BAU	60%	
Share of products collected CBBE	2023=60%;2030=80%;2050=100%	
Fraction resold and reused BAU	1.92%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)
Fraction resold and reused CBBE	2023=1.92%;2030=20%;2050=50%	
Fraction of sorted chemicals sold domestically BAU	10%	(Kerstens & Bessembinders, 2020)
Fraction of sorted chemicals sold domestically CBBE	2023=10%; 2030=10%; 2050=20%	
Fraction recycled and reused BAU	16%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)
Fraction recycled and reused CBBE	2023=16%; 2030=30%; 2050= 50%	

Share of Materials to incineration	25%	(Van Eijk, Sederel, Groen, & van den Beuken, 2023)
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7.4 Employment

The employment structure in the model is driven by the waste and products generated to demonstrate the level of employment under different scenarios. The employment level is decided by exogenous variables that determine the level of employment per material or product. The model tracks downstream employment, such as the employment per recycling material, etc. The equations are as follows:

$$\text{employment for product repair and reuse} = \text{employment per ton of product repaired and reused} * \text{products resold and reused}$$

This formulation allows for endogenously calculating the level of employment based on the exogenous variable of employment per ton. While the model is for the most part not parametrized, it is set up to accommodate the use of additional inputs, as shown in Table 48.

Table 48: Parameters used for the employment model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Employment per unit sold	0.00157486	(Eurostat, 2024)
Employment per ton of product repaired and reused	Not parametrized	
Employment per unit collected and sorted		
Employment per unit recycled		
Employment per unit of material repaired and reused		
Employment per unit of waste landfilled		
Employment per unit of water consumed		

Employment per unit of energy consumed		
Employment per unit of waste incinerated		

7.5 Energy Consumption

The chemical industry in the Netherlands mainly consumed carbon-intensive fossil fuels for its production. The model structure accounts for this by using the energy intensities for the year 2022 and endogenous material consumption. The energy intensity values are shown in Table 49.

The fuel cost structure derives its equation from the 2022 price of energy and energy consumption to find the annual energy costs. The total energy efficiency investments are calculated by determining the difference between energy costs in the BAU scenario compared to the CBBE scenario, utilizing the exogenous variable for energy savings per investment (see Figure 77).

Figure 77: Causal tree for Total Energy Efficiency Investments, chemical industry model

The industry emission is the product of the endogenous energy consumption per energy type and the associated emission factor.

$$\text{Total CO2e emissions in tons} = \frac{(\text{fuel electricity emissions} + \text{fuel natural gas emissions} + \text{heat emissions} + \text{non renewable waste emissions} + \text{oil and petroleum emissions}) / \text{kg to ton}}{\text{kg to ton}}$$

The equation sums up the emissions from various sources, including electricity generation, fuel combustion, heating processes, and waste disposal, and then converts the total emissions from kilograms to tons. It provides a comprehensive measure of the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the industry processes.

Table 49: Energy intensities used for the energy consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Intensity	0.00242654 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Heat Intensity	0.00175332 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Electricity Intensity	0.000468198 GWH/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Oil and Petroleum	0.00371134TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)
Non-renewable waste intensity	2e-009 TJ/ton	(Eurostat, 2022)

7.6 Energy Price

The data for energy prices is the static value for the average annual price with the data selected as close as possible to the year 2022. The values of which can be found in Table 50. As Europe mainly uses electricity for heating, the same values are used for both prices.

Table 50: Energy prices used for the energy consumption model component, chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Natural Gas Price	1.3076e-006 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Electricity Price	1.32444e-007 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Heat Price	1.32444e-007 Euro/TJ	(Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023)
Oil and Petroleum Price	2.00454e-005 Euro/TJ	(European Commission, 2024)
Nonrenewable waste price	0.0002412 Euro/TJ	(Koldenhof, 2023)

7.7 Material Costs

The costs of materials are contingent upon the input materials utilized. Given that the model assesses the chemical industry at an aggregate level, the cost of materials is averaged to euros per ton of chemicals produced. However, the cost of materials would vary if the policy's share of recycled chemicals increased. The following equation was utilized to compute the cost of materials, considering the proportion of recycled fibres used.

$$\text{Annual Industry Cost for Materials} = (\text{products dismantled for materials recycle and reuse} * \text{Cost of Recycled Fibers}) + (\text{Cost of Input Materials} * \text{material consumption})$$

The parameters used for the equation can be found in Table 51.

Table 51: Material costs used in the chemical industry model

Variable	Value	Source
Cost per ton of recycled materials	Not parametrized	
Cost per ton of materials	Not parametrized	

7.8 Value addition

The economic activity of the industry generates value addition which contributes to the national GDP of the country. The value addition is determined by the purchase rate and the real value addition time series and forecast. It is the sum of chemical purchases and value addition per ton. Two variations of the value addition per ton are calculated, one for conventional production and one for bio-based production. The module considers the value addition from purchases, including reused chemicals, but does not disaggregate between the two.

Figure 78: Cause tree for Value addition in the chemical sector

The historical part of the value addition is calculated from historical production (cefic, 2023; Eurostat, 2023b; ONEPOINTE SOLUTIONS, 2020; UN Population Division, 2022) and the value addition (Eurostat, 2024), using the equation below.

$$Value\ addition\ intensity = \frac{Value\ addition_t}{Production_t}$$

The forecast for value addition in the conventional scenario is the real GDP growth rate from the IMF World Economic Outlook extended to 2060. For the chemical value addition this means 1.63% growth annually from 2028 onwards. For the alternative scenario, the value addition adds an additional percentage increase on top from literature (Annapure, Sathyanaryana, & Gupta, 2022; Taneja et al., 2023; Alikabara et al, 2021; Simanke et al, 2024; Vivekanandhan, Zarrinbakhsh, & Mohanty, 2021). The literature ranges from 0.01% additional value addition to 30 times in the case of a full transition. Hence, each country has its future bio-based value addition calibrated within the range of 0.01% to 5%. In the case of the Netherlands, and thus, the chemicals sector the additional value addition increase was calibrated to 5% (see

).

Figure 79: Value addition conventional and bio-based for Netherland's chemical industry

The GDP of the chemical industry is calculated by summing the value addition, purchases, and the bio-based share of the industry, which is influenced by the active policy levers during the simulation. To determine the bio-based value addition, we consider the share of production that is bio-based along with a counterfactual scenario, providing a comprehensive value addition that incorporates both bio-based and conventional components. The equation for this calculation includes the sum of chemical purchases, conventional value addition, and the bio-based shares of both textile purchases and value addition. By accounting for these factors, we accurately reflect the contribution of bio-based and conventional elements to the industry's GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{real value added new purchases chemicals industry=} \\
 & ((\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin product} * (1 - \text{share of textile products manufactured using bio-} \\
 & \text{based products})) + (\text{product purchase} * \text{value added per virgin bio-based material} * (\text{share of textile products} \\
 & \text{manufactured using bio-based products}))) * \text{COVID shock on capital}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the textile GDP is a sub-sector of industry GDP, the real chemical GDP is subtracted from the real GDP industry before being re-added to the formulation so that the economic value is not double counted.

Figure 80: Use tree for real GDP textile industry

8 DOCUMENTATION OF THE GREEN ECONOMY MODEL (GEM)

The following paragraphs provide an overview of the model and a more detailed documentation is available in Bassi et al. (Bassi, Garrido, Harsono, & Pallaske, 2024).

The Green Economy Model (GEM) is a System Thinking based, System Dynamics macro, dynamic, integrated assessment representation of the socio-economy, and the natural capital that supports it, at country level (Bassi, 2015; Pallaske, Bassi, Garrido, & Guzzetti, 2023).

GEM is designed to inform policymaking towards sustainable development. It allows forecasting and assessing the outcomes of various policies and investments in relation to medium- and long-term national development targets. By offering a systemic approach, GEM forecasts the outcomes of action and inaction across sectors, actors, dimensions of development and over time. Further, GEM enables the formulation of policies and investment packages that result in a more inclusive,

robust, and resilient outlook for the country. At the same time, by means of co-creation, GEM supports the creation of a better understanding of the co-benefits associated with sustainable policies and investments, including on climate action, under different climate scenarios.

Figure 81 presents the generalized underlying structure of GEM. Figure 82 presents instead a sub-system diagram of the model. The former shows how four key capitals (built, social, human and natural) are interconnected, and how they contribute to shaping future trends across social, economic and environmental indicators. Specifically, feedback loops can be identified that are reinforcing (R), in all areas pertaining to economic growth and social development. These are driven by investments and knowledge creation, and enabled by the availability of natural capital, which, if not properly managed, can constrain economic growth (hence the balancing loops -(B)-identified in the diagram). Policies can be implemented to promote sustainable consumption and production, decoupling economic growth from resource use (also through education and behavioural change), to mitigate the exploitation of natural capital and generate a stronger and more resilient green growth.

GEM has been applied to more than 50 countries and was designed to include all key sectors that are relevant for future development, for instance in the context of low carbon development (HMIT, 2021; BAPPENAS, 2021) and green recovery packages (UNEP, 2020). These include, among others: population, food demand and supply, land use and land cover, economic activity (via the use of national accounts), employment, access to health care, education, energy demand and supply, air emissions, water pollution, and climate trends. The model also provides an economic valuation for several externalities, including GHG emissions (social cost of carbon), air pollution, wastewater, waste, traffic-related impacts (e.g. accidents, noise), the opportunity cost of water (from savings in the agriculture sector) and biodiversity.

Figure 81: Overview of GEM, built on (Bassi, 2015).

GEM is built using the System Dynamics (SD) methodology, serving primarily as a *knowledge integrator*. SD is a form of computer simulation modelling designed to facilitate a comprehensive approach to development planning in the medium to long term (Meadows, 1980; Randers, 1980; Richardson & Pugh, 1981; Forrester, 2002). SD operates by simulating differential equations with “*what if*” scenarios, explicitly represents stocks and flows (critical to estimate climate change impacts on infrastructure, and how such impacts accumulate over time to affect economic productivity, among other indicators), can integrate optimization and econometrics and support model coupling (e.g. in conjunction with spatially explicit models, sectoral models for energy and the economy).

The purpose of using SD for the development and application of GEM is not to make precise predictions of the future, nor to optimize performance; rather, GEM applications are used to inform policy formulation, forecasting policy outcomes (both desirable and undesirable) and leading to the creation of a resilient and well-balanced strategy (Roberts, Andersen, Deal, Garet, & Shaffer, 1983; Probst & Bassi, 2014). Such an approach is consistent with the thinking framework of policymakers, who weigh *sets* of outcomes on the basis of political, technical and institutional preferences in choosing from among policy packages.

All GEM applications include four key capitals (physical, human, social and natural) as interconnected via the explicit representation of feedback loops (reinforcing or balancing)¹. Policies can be implemented to strengthen growth (reinforcing loops, e.g. investments in physical capital accumulate capital stock, which, other things equal, increases output potential, production, aggregate demand, including investment, further increasing capital and output); or curb change (e.g. by strengthening balancing loops). In the context of climate action, we generally find that transition investments directly stimulate new growth, while investments in climate resilience reduce costs and free up resources, thereby enabling new growth indirectly.

Among the many feedback relationships represented by GEM, there are two that are worth highlighting, considering how central they are for explaining the connectedness of climate, environmental and socio-economic outcomes, which is, in turn, central for the design of robust development policies. The first one refers to impacts on what mainstream models refer to as Total Factor Productivity (TFP). TFP in the model is impacted by technology, infrastructure (e.g. the road network and access to electricity), energy productivity (i.e. considering the cost of energy as a ratio of GDP), air pollution, weather (e.g. temperature) and extreme weather events. As a result, investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy, to cite two examples, both reduce energy consumption and spending (possibly resulting in higher GDP), and reduce air pollution (also possibly resulting in higher GDP, but via a different channel). The second one refers to a feedback loop that governs linkages between climate, environment (including policies) and the socio-economy. This feedback loop considers the availability of natural resources, and impacts of land cover change on ecosystem service provisioning, which goes on to affect economic activity, as well as access to natural resources. These dynamics are represented via the use of feedback loops in the model, resulting in circular relations that may highlight the simultaneous emergence of short-term benefits and medium-term challenges, or vice versa, depending on the scenarios simulated.

¹ In a reinforcing loop, a change in one direction is compounded by more change. Under a reinforcing loop, policies or shocks that move a variable in one direction transmit through the system in a way that leads to further increases in such variables over time. For example, money in a savings account generates interest, which increases the balance in the savings account and earns more interest. Balancing loops, in contrast, counter change in one direction with change in the opposite direction.

Figure 82: Sub-system diagram presenting the key sectoral components of GEM.

8.1 Population

The population module provides an overview of the development of total population, births and deaths over time. The population module contains the stock of population, which is affected by the three flows: births, migration and deaths. The stock of population changes based on the integration of its three flows:

$$\text{Population } t+1 = \text{Population } t_0 + \text{births } t_0 + \text{migration } t_0 - \text{deaths } t_0$$

The number of births depends on the total fertility rate and the stock level of the population. Births are calculated based on the following equation:

$$\text{Births} = \text{Population} * \text{POPULATION GROWTH RATE}(\text{Time})$$

The historical population growth rate is hereby obtained from national statistics, and the forecast is calibrated to match the population forecast provided by the United Nations (UN Population Division, 2022).

Migration rate is calibrated to match the historical development of population and assumed zero in the future. In the Honduras model, migration is a bi-flow, which means that it can increase or decrease total population depending on whether it is positive or negative.

The number of deaths depends on the stock level of population and the average life expectancy. Total population is divided by the average life expectancy to obtain the annual numbers of deaths. In the current version of the model, life expectancy was obtained from the United Nations Population Division (2022).

$$\text{Deaths} = \text{Population} / \text{AVERAGE LIFE EXPECTANCY TABLE}(\text{Time})$$

8.2 Household accounts

The household account module serves for the calculation of nominal GDP, disposable income and private consumption, savings and investment. It provides information concerning the development of these variables over time and allows for the assessment of policy impacts on household-specific key indicators (Table 52).

Table 52: Overview of data sources for the household accounts module

Variable	Type
Nominal production (GDP)	Time series
Disposable income	Time series
Private consumption	Time series
Private investment	Time series
Nominal exports	Time series

Nominal imports	Time series
-----------------	-------------

The household module contains household investment and consumption and provides an indication about the real disposable household income. Household revenues are hereby calculated as the sum of nominal GDP, interest on domestic debt, private current transfers and subsidies and transfers.

$$\text{Household revenues} = \text{interest on domestic debt} + \text{private current transfers} + \text{subsidies and transfers} + \text{nominal production}$$

Total disposable income is calculated as household revenues minus government domestic revenues. Disposable income is used for the calculation of private savings and consumption, and real disposable income per capita. Real disposable income per capita is calculated by dividing disposable income by total population and the GDP deflator. The relative value of per capita real disposable income, current real disposable income per capita divided by its initial value, affects the propensity to consume and hence private consumption and private savings.

$$\text{propensity to consume} = \text{INITIAL PROPENSITY TO CONSUME}(\text{Time}) * \text{relative pc real disposable income} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF PROPENSITY TO CONSUME TO INCOME} * \text{covid impact on propensity to consume}$$

In addition to the relative real disposable income, COVID-19 impacts on the propensity to consume are implemented. The impacts of COVID-19 on the propensity to consume are based on COVID-19 employment impacts and an elasticity.

$$\text{covid impact on propensity to consume} = \text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{COVID19 SWITCH}=1 : \text{AND: DURATION OF COVID IMPACTS TABLE}(\text{Time}) > 0, \text{average covid impact on employment} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF PRIVATE CONSUMPTION TO COVID}, 1)$$

The IF THEN ELSE function allows for activating the impacts of COVID-19 in the simulations. If the COVID19 switch has a value of “1” (= active) and capital impacts of COVID-19 are active (variable “duration of covid impacts table”), the model will use COVID-19 employment impacts and the elasticity of private consumption to estimate the impact on the propensity to consume. If the switch has a value of “0”, the variable takes a value of “1” (neutral) and no COVID-19 impacts on propensity to consume are simulated.

The propensity to consume and disposable income are multiplied to calculate total private consumption. Private savings are calculated as the difference between disposable income and private consumption.

$$\text{Private savings} = \text{disposable income} - \text{private consumption}$$

Private investments are determined based on private savings, the share of private savings for private investment and capital, corrected for monetary flows related to government financing, whereby the latter one is based on historical data.

$$private\ savings\ for\ private\ investment = private\ savings * share\ of\ savings\ invested - government\ domestic\ financing$$

Nominal consumption and nominal investment are calculated as the sum of government and private consumption and government and private investments respectively. Figure 83 provides an overview of the variables used for calculating nominal consumption and Figure 84 shows the variables used for calculating nominal investment.

. Figure 83: Causes tree nominal consumption

Figure 84: Causes tree nominal investment

The causes tree above illustrates that GEM also provides the feature of simulating government recovery packages for addressing COVID-19 impacts, by allowing additional investments to be simulated. If the COVID19 recovery switch has a value of “1” (=policy active), the model will use a different time series for calculating government consumption compared to the BAU. This change allows to keep government consumption constant, and increase government investment temporarily for the duration of the recovery actions. The above highlights that both nominal consumption and investment are affected by COVID-19 impacts.

8.3 Government accounts

The government accounts module provides an overview of government revenues, investments and debt. It allows for analysing different public spending strategies and is used as the entry point for the simulation of a government stimulus post COVID-19. Key indicators of the government accounts module and their respective sources are presented in Table 53.

Table 53: Overview of data sources for the government accounts module

Variable	Type
Government revenues	Time series
Government investment	Time series
Desired government deficit	Time series
Public debt	Time series
Interest on public debt	Time series
Government revenues	Time series

The government accounts module captures government revenues and grants and provides information on total government consumption and investment. Total government revenue is the sum of government domestic revenue and revenues from grants, both calculated as a share of nominal GDP (named nominal production in the model). The causes tree in Figure 85 summarizes the variables used to calculate total government revenues.

Figure 85: Causes tree total government revenue

The sum of total government revenue and government domestic financing constitutes the government budget. Government financing is defined as total government revenues multiplied by the desired government deficit, a time series function estimated based on historical data. As illustrated in the uses tree in Figure 86, the government budget is used to calculate the government budget after interest, non-development expenditure and development expenditure.

Figure 86: Uses tree government budget

The government budget after interest is calculated by deducting interest payments on public debt from the government budget. The budget excluding interest serves for the calculation of government consumption and government investment, using the share of government consumption over total expenditure. Government consumption is calculated by multiplying the share of government consumption over total expenditure by the budget excluding interest; government investment is calculated by multiplying the budget excluding interest by one minus the share of government consumption over total expenditure, as illustrated by the equation below.

$$\text{government investment} = \text{government budget after interest} * (1 - \text{share of government consumption over total expenditure})$$

Non-development expenditure is the sum of interest on public debt and the share of government budget used for administrative purposes.

$$\text{Non-development expenditure} = \text{interests on public debt} + \text{government budget} * \text{ADMINISTRATIVE EXPENDITURE AS SHARE OF BUDGET} * \text{GDP Deflator}$$

Development expenditure, which is used to calculate investments in health care, education and resource efficiency, is equal to the government budget corrected for non-development expenditure.

$$\text{development expenditure} = \text{MAX}(\text{government budget} - \text{non development expenditure}, 0)$$

A MAX function is used to avoid that development expenditure becomes smaller than zero, which would be equivalent to negative investment.

Investments in health care, education and resource efficiency are calculated by multiplying government development expenditure by the desired share of development expenditure invested in health care, education and resource efficiency respectively. The desired investment shares for health care and education are calibrated to ensure that the resulting investments are consistent with historical data.

$$\text{education expenditure} = \text{development expenditure} * \text{desired share of development expenditure for education}$$

8.4 Land use

The land use module provides information about aggregate land use and land use change over time. This module allows for assessing the impacts of development policies on land use and potential conversions of land resulting from their implementation. The land use module contains four stocks; forest land, agriculture land, settlement land and fallow land. Five flows are used to capture land use change over time. Stocks and the respective flows are illustrated in Table 54.

Table 54: Overview of stocks and flows in the land use module

Stock	Inflow(s)	Outflow(s)
Forest land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fallow to forest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest to settlement Forest to agriculture
Agriculture land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest to agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture to fallow
Settlement land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forest to settlement Fallow to settlement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Fallow land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture to fallow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fallow to forest Fallow to settlement

Agriculture land, and changes therein, are caused by land conversion for agriculture (forest to agriculture and fallow to agriculture) and the depreciation of agriculture land (agriculture to fallow). The flow “forest to agriculture” is calculated by the equation below.

$$\text{Forest to agriculture} = \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in agriculture land} + \text{agriculture to fallow}, \text{Forest Land} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FOREST LAND})$$

A MIN function is used to ensure that land conversion is constrained if the desired change in agriculture exceeds the available forest area for conversion. The desired change in agriculture hereby indicates the difference between established and required agriculture land. The desired change in agriculture is the gap between desired agriculture land and currently established agriculture land. The desired amount of agriculture land is hereby based on total population and per capita agriculture land multiplier.

$$\text{desired agriculture land} = \text{Population} * \text{desired agriculture land per capita}$$

The stock of settlement land has two inflows, assuming that forest and fallow land can be converted for the expansion of urban areas. Land conversion for settlement land is based on the desired settlement land, which is calculated by multiplying population by desired settlement land per capita. The equations are formulated based on the assumption that, as long as there is fallow land available for conversion, there will be no deforestation for establishing settlement land. The following equation is used for calculating the conversion of fallow to settlement land.

$$\text{Fallow to settlement} = \text{MAX}(0, \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in settlement land}, \text{Fallow Land} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FALLOW LAND}))$$

A MIN and a MAX function are used for the calculation of land conversion from fallow to settlement land. The MIN function ensures that the conversion of land from settlement land cannot exceed the amount of fallow land currently available (same as for the conversion of forest land for agriculture). In the event that the stock of settlement land is higher than the desired settlement land (indicating a negative desired land conversion for settlement and), there would be a flow

from settlement land back to fallow land. The MAX function ensures that the current level of settlement land is maintained in case of such an event.

In the case of land conversion for settlement land, forest land serves as a buffer. This means that the conversion of forest to settlement land is only assumed if the amount of fallow land is below the amount required for converting the desired amount.

$$\text{Forest to settlement} = \text{MAX}(0, \text{MIN}(\text{desired change in settlement land} - \text{waste to settlement}, \text{Forest} / \text{TIME TO CONVERT FOREST LAND}))$$

As in the case of fallow to settlement, a MIN and a MAX function are used to ensure that land conversion takes place based on land available, and that no reduction of settlement land occurs.

The stock of forest land changes based on land conversion for agriculture and settlement land and the regeneration of forests from fallow land. The outflows of the forest stock, forest to settlement and forest to agriculture, are documented above. The regeneration of forests is the sum of forest regeneration, calculated by dividing the stock of fallow land by the average forest regeneration time, and annual reforestation. The equation for the inflow to the forest stock is presented below.

$$\text{Fallow to forest} = \text{Fallow Land} / \text{AVERAGE FOREST REGENERATION TIME}$$

8.5 Carbon stock and emissions from land

The carbon stock module provides information about Ethiopia's carbon stock and changes therein caused by land conversion. The module is used to assess how policy-induced land use changes affect the country's carbon stock and land emissions.

Table 55: Overview of data sources for the carbon stock module

Name of variable	Type	Source for estimation
Carbon factor forest land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor settlement land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor agriculture land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)
Carbon factor fallow land	Constant	Based on (IPCC, 2006)

Carbon stocks are calculated by multiplying the four different land use stocks by a respective carbon factor. The sum of the four carbon stocks represents the total carbon stock. Figure 87 shows the variables used for the calculation of the total carbon stock.

Figure 87: Causes tree total carbon stock

Annual emissions from land are calculated based on land conversion. The calculations are based on the five flows described in the documentation of the land use module and the carbon factors applied to the four land use stocks. The cause tree in Figure 88 shows the variables used for the calculation of the net change in carbon stock from land conversion and the CO₂e emissions from land.

Figure 88: Causes tree CO₂e emissions from land

To estimate the change in carbon stock caused by land use change, the model calculates the net change in total CO₂ that is caused by land conversion. This is done by calculating the difference in carbon stock from the land use class subject to conversion and the target land use class. The equation below illustrates the calculation of the change in carbon stock occurring if forest land is converted to agriculture land.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to forest} = \\ & \text{forest to agriculture} * \text{adjusted carbon factor agriculture for land use calculations} \\ & - \text{forest to agriculture} * \text{adjusted carbon factor forest for land use calculations} \end{aligned}$$

The same approach is applied to calculate the changes in carbon stock for the other four flows. The net change in carbon stock is then calculated as the sum of the individual changes in carbon stock caused by the conversion of land.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{net change in carbon stock from land conversion} = \\ & \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to fallow} + \text{change in carbon stock from agriculture to forest} \\ & + \text{change in carbon stock from fallow to forest} + \text{change in carbon stock from forest to settlement} \\ & + \text{change in carbon stock from fallow to settlement} \end{aligned}$$

8.6 Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The Gross Domestic Product module provides information about the development of total real GDP, the three sectoral GDPs (agriculture, industry and services) and their respective shares in total real GDP. This module allows for assessing policy impacts on total real GDP and real GDP growth as well potential changes in a nation's economy, indicated by changes in sectoral contributions to real GDP.

The agriculture, industry and services modules serve for the calculation of the GDP of the sectors that have not been disaggregated for the analysis of the economy. All three sectors are described in this section. While the same structural building blocks are used to represent industry and services in the model, the agriculture module is more disaggregated and hence described in a separate section.

8.6.1 Agriculture GDP

This module provides information about agriculture productivity and employment over time. Key indicators are agriculture real GDP and its growth rate, employment in agriculture and indicated investment in agriculture. The module allows for assessing the impacts of development policies on agriculture GDP and employment, such as for example the reduction of losses during the transport of goods to market.

Agriculture real GDP is calculated based on the real agriculture production rate and a value added per ton of produce multiplier. The variable "real agriculture production rate" accounts for pre-harvest losses and loss of produce during transport to market (see crop production section).

$$\text{Real GDP agriculture} = \text{real agriculture production rate} * \text{VALUE ADDED PER TON PRODUCED}(\text{Time})$$

The growth rate of agriculture real GDP is calculated using a TREND function, which estimates the change in agriculture real GDP on an annual basis.

$$\text{real gdp growth rate agriculture} = \text{TREND}(\text{real gdp agriculture}, "1 \text{ YEAR DELAY TIME}", \text{INITIAL REAL GDP GROWTH RATE AGRICULTURE})$$

Employment in agriculture is calculated based on total agriculture land. The equation below is used to calculate employment in agriculture.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{employment agriculture} = & \text{land used for crop production} * \text{EMPLOYMENT PER HECTARE OF AGRICULTURE LAND TABLE}(\text{Time}) \\ & * (1 - \text{share of agriculture sustainable}) + \text{land used for crop production} \\ & * \text{EMPLOYMENT PER HECTARE OF AGRICULTURE LAND TABLE}(\text{Time}) * \text{share of agriculture sustainable} \\ & * (1 + \text{ADDITIONAL EMPLOYMENT FROM SUSTAINABLE CROPLAND}) \end{aligned}$$

This formulation indicates that agriculture employment is the sum of employment in conventional and sustainable agriculture. The underlying assumption for this equation is that sustainable agriculture has a higher labour intensity per hectare, which is accounted for by using the share of sustainable cropland and a multiplier.

8.6.2 Industry and services GDP

For the industry and services modules, the supply side approach is used. Throughout this section, the 'industry module' will serve as an example to illustrate equations and variables that are used

to represent the residual sectors. Table 56 provides an overview of the data sources used for calibrating real GDP, employment and total factor productivity.

Table 56: Overview of data sources for the industry and services GDP module

Variable	Type
Total employment	Time series
Industry real GDP	Time series
Services real GDP	Time series
Employment in industry	Time series
Employment in services	Time series
Total employment	Time series

Capital, labour and productivity are used to calculate the performance of the residual sectors. The stock of Industry Capital changes based on the following equation

$$\text{Industry Capital}_{t+1} = \text{Industry Capital}_{t0} + \text{investment industry}_{t0} - \text{depreciation}_{t0} - \text{loss of industry capital due to floods}_{t0}$$

Investment in industry is defined as nominal investment industry, which is calculated by multiplying total nominal investment (the sum of private and government investment) by the share invested in industry. The formulation is based on the assumption that the industry will invest in capital to maintain or extend production.

The depreciation of industry capital is calculated by dividing the current Industry Capital by the average lifetime of industry capital. The depreciation captures machinery that reaches the end of its lifetime, or facilities that are outdated. Relative industry capital, an indicator of how much Industry Capital has changed compared to the beginning of the simulation, is calculated by dividing the stock level of Industry Capital by its initial value.

In addition, the model simulates the impacts of COVID-19 on productive capital by inducing an additional capital outflow between 2020 and 2023 (assuming 3 waves of the pandemic). The equation for the depreciation of industry capital is presented below.

$$\text{depreciation of industry capital} = \text{Capital Industry} / \text{average capital life} * \text{covid effect on capital industry}$$

Employment in industry is calculated by multiplying Industry Capital by the labour intensity of the industry sector, an employment factor indicating the employment generated per unit of capital, and the COVID-19 impact on employment.

$$\text{employment industry} = \text{Capital Industry} * \text{real labor intensity industry} * \text{covid19 effect on industry employment}$$

The labour intensity of the industrial sector is affected by the relative labour cost, which affects sectoral employment depending on the cost of labour. If unemployment increases, the cost of labour declines and allows for increased hiring to take place. A decrease in unemployment on the other hand would increase labour cost and curb job creation.

$$\text{real labor intensity industry} = \text{Labor Intensity Industry} / \text{Actual Relative Labor Cost}$$

Relative employment in the industry sector is calculated by dividing the employment in industry by its initial value.

Industry GDP represents the sector's economic performance. It is calculated by multiplying initial GDP industry by production multipliers that account for employment and capital (with a respective elasticity using the Cobb-Douglas formulation) and total factor productivity. The following formulation is used for the calculation of real industry GDP:

$$\text{Real GDP industry} = \text{initial GDP industry} * \text{relative capital}^{\text{capital elasticity industry}} * \text{relative employment level industry}^{\text{labor elasticity}} * \text{total factor productivity industry}$$

Figure 89 presents a cause tree that depicts the variables used for calculating real industry GDP and determining total factor productivity of the industry sector. Total factor productivity depends on the development of the energy bill, health care, adult literacy, technology, wastewater treatment and CO₂e emissions. The following equation is used for calculating Relative production in the industry sector.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Total factor productivity industry} = & \text{effect of technology on capital productivity} * \text{effect of emissions on total factor productivity} & * \text{effect of} \\
 & \text{energy bill on industry tfp} * \text{effect of roads on total factor productivity} \\
 & * \text{effect of habitat quality on productivity} * \text{effect of WBGT on labor productivity}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 89: Causes tree real GDP industry

Table 57 provides the equations used to determine the effects constituting total factor productivity with their respective equations.

Table 57: Documentation of effects constituting total factor productivity industry

Effect name	Effect equation
effect of technology	Tech ^ elasticity of industry tfp to technology
effect of emissions	DELAY31 (relative total co2e emissions from energy^elasticity of TFP to CO2e emissions, "1 year delay time", 1)
effect of energy bill	DELAY31 (relative energy bill as share of GDP^elasticity of energy bill on industry TFP, "1 year delay time", 1)
effect of roads on TFP	DELAY3 (relative km of roads^elasticity of industry tfp to roads, "2 year delay time")

Effect of habitat quality	IF THEN ELSE (Time>2020,indicated effect of habitat quality on productivity/effect of habitat quality on productivity in 2020,1)
effect of Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)	effect of extreme temperature on labor productivity^elasticity of labor productivity to WBGT

8.7 Employment and technology

This module provides an overview of both sectoral and total employment and the development of technology over time. It allows to assess employment impacts of policy interventions and for changing trends in technological development underlying the analysis.

Table 58: Overview of data sources for the employment and technology module

Name of variable	Type
Employment in agriculture	Time series
Employment in industry	Time series
Employment in services	Time series
Annual change in technology	Constant
Labor force participation rate	Time series
Average annual salary	Time series

Total employment is calculated as the sum of sectoral employment from agriculture, industry and services. Figure 90 shows the variables used for estimating total employment using a cause tree. The equations used for estimating sectoral employment are described in the previous section.

Figure 90: Causes tree total employment

Total employment and the labour force are used to calculate the unemployment rate. The labour force is hereby calculated by multiplying total population by the labour force participation rate. The unemployment rate is calculated using a MAX function to avoid the variable from taking negative values.

$$\text{Unemployment rate} = \text{MAX}(1 - \text{total employment} / \text{labor force}, 0)$$

Technology, or ‘Tech’ in the model, is used to affect total factor productivity, is modelled as a stock with an initial value of one (“1”) and an annual growth rate. It is an index that increases steadily over time, representing improvements in machinery as well as automation of processes.

8.8 Energy demand

The model projects national energy consumption by sector and source, from 2000 to 2050. Energy consumption is then multiplied by GHG emission factors to obtain total national emissions from the use of energy.

The main structural assumptions of the model are (see Figure 91):

- Final energy consumption is estimated considering (1) indicated demand (including the effect of GDP, population and energy efficiency); (2) the price effect; and (3) the substitution effect. Items (1) and (2) are used to estimate *demand for energy services*.
- The potential for fuel substitution is represented by the ratio of an energy price over the national weighted average energy price. This implies that an energy source will become more attractive if its price increases less than others when subsidies are removed.
- It is assumed that price effects require a 1-year delay to influence energy consumption.

One of the main drivers of the model is energy price, which can be modified in two ways: (1) by setting baseline medium to longer-term trends (which is an endogenous calculation for electricity) and (2) by removing fossil fuel subsidies. The removal of subsidies increases energy prices, which lowers energy demand in two possible ways: energy is becoming more expensive and consumption is reduced to offset the growth in expenditure, and, if energy services are required, the use of (previously) subsidized fossil fuels declines and consumption of now comparatively cheaper fuels increases. GHG emissions are affected by both the reduction of energy consumption and the change in fuel mix, and the model analyses these effects separately. As a result, the model allows us to estimate the impact of fossil fuel subsidy removal on GHG emissions, and compare such reduction to other possible intervention options (e.g. investments and/or mandates on energy efficiency and renewable energy). Emission reductions can also be estimated as a result of the reallocation of subsidy savings, such as through investments in RE and EE.

Figure 91: Energy demand estimation sketch.

Several variables and equations are used to estimate energy flows (which are measured in terajoule per year, TJ/year) and emissions (which are measured in tons per year, ton/year).

To begin with, indicated sectoral energy demand (*coal* is presented as an example) is calculated using the initial value for 2000, multiplying it by relative GDP and relative population (both | energy efficiency (also indexed to 2000). The use of subscripts, ‘sector’ in the example provided below, allows for calculating energy demand for the residential, commercial, industrial, and transport sectors within the same variable.

$$\text{Indicated Coal Demand}[\text{sector}] = \frac{(\text{INITIAL COAL DEMAND TABLE}[\text{sector}] * \text{Relative GDP} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO GDP}[\text{sector}] * \text{Relative Population} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO POPULATION}) / \text{Relative Energy Efficiency}}$$

The price effect is then added, simply taking indicated demand (presented above) and multiplying it by relative energy price (indexed to 2000) and raised to the power of a price elasticity.

The removal of fossil fuel subsidies is reflected in energy price changes. When subsidies are removed, it is assumed that energy prices increase for all sectors (unless it is known that subsidies are allocated to specific users). Users can indicate the extent to which subsidies are removed and the timeline (e.g. full removal, linearly, by 2030).

$$\text{"Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} = \text{Indicated Coal Demand}[\text{sector}] * \text{Relative Coal Price} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE}[\text{sector}]$$

Next, the substitution effect is considered. The formulation is the same as the one used for incorporating the price effect, but a delay of 1 year is used to represent the lag existing between price changes and demand (or consumption) changes.

$$\text{"Coal Demand (With Substitution Effect)"[sector]} = \text{DELAY N}(\text{"Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} * \text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE}[\text{sector}], \text{TIME TO ADAPT DEMAND TO PRICE CHANGES}, (\text{"Indicated Coal Demand (With Price Effect)"[sector]} * \text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} \wedge \text{ELASTICITY OF COAL DEMAND TO COAL PRICE}[\text{sector}]), 3)$$

The potential for substitution from one energy source to the other, due to price changes (e.g. as a result to fossil fuel subsidy removal), is incorporated here by using the ratio of energy source price (e.g. coal) over the average energy price of the country (estimated as a weighted average of all energy prices). This ratio is also indexed, to ensure consistency with the use of elasticities.

$$\text{"Coal Price - Substitution"} = \text{DELAY N}((\text{Relative Coal Price} / \text{Relative Weighted Average Energy Price}), 1, 1, 1)$$

Indicated energy demand (including the price effect) is used to estimate the total indicated energy demand (which is also demand for energy services), which is the total energy that has to be guaranteed at the country level. The potential for substitution is instead used to estimate the actual share of energy consumption by source. As a result, a normalization is performed multiplying total indicated energy demand by the shares obtained from the inclusion of the substitution effect.

$$\text{Normalized Coal Demand}[\text{sector}] = \text{Total Indicated Country Energy Demand} * \text{Normalized Coal Share Of Energy Demand}[\text{sector}]$$

8.9 Energy bill

The energy bill provides an overview of the country-level energy cost by type of fuel and the relation between energy cost and total real GDP. The latter is used to estimate energy cost impacts on total factor productivity. The cause tree in Figure 92 presents the variables that are used to calculate the energy bill.

Figure 92: Causes tree Energy bill

In all cases, the cost of energy is calculated using the normalized country energy demand by fuel, the price of energy and, where required, a conversion factor to align units of measure. The equation used for calculating the country level cost of petroleum is described below.

$$\text{cost of petroleum} = \text{total country normalized petroleum demand} * \text{petroleum price} * \text{conversion tj to liter of petroleum}$$

The energy bill, calculated as the sum of costs across all fuel categories, is converted from USD to local currency units (LCU) using the exchange rate. To calculate the impacts of energy cost on total factor productivity for industry and services, the energy bill as a share of nominal GDP is calculated.

$$\text{energy bill as share of gdp} = \frac{\text{energy bill in lcu}}{\text{nominal production}}$$

The relative energy bill as share of GDP, an index calculated by dividing the current energy bill as share of GDP by its initial value in the year 2000, is used to calibrate the impacts of energy cost on industry and services TFP. The use tree for the relative energy bill as share of GDP is presented in Figure 93.

Figure 93: Uses tree Relative energy bill as share of GDP

8.10 Power generation capacity

The power generation module captures the demand for electricity, transmission losses and required and current power generation capacity. The module uses the total normalized electricity demand as input to assess electricity generation by technology and forecast future capacity requirements. It further provides information about total electricity generation, both by technology and system-wide, and the shares of generation by technology. The power generation module uses the subscript [power generation technology], which allows the use of the same structural components to estimate capacity, generation and cost for the 14 technologies presented in Table 59.

Table 59: Power generation technologies considered in GEM

Power generation technologies	
Diesel and fuel oil	Hydropower (large scale)
Cogeneration	Hydropower (small scale)
Gas turbine	Solar power (utility scale)
Steam coal	Solar PV (rooftop)
Nuclear	Wind (onshore)
Biomass	Wind (offshore)
Geothermal	Waste generation

Power generation capacity is represented using two stocks: *Power Generation Capacity Under Construction* and *Power Generation Capacity*. The installation and usage of power generation capacity is driven by the desired electricity generation rate, which considers both imports and transmission losses.

$$\text{desired electricity generation} = \text{electricity demand in mwh} * (1 + \text{TRANSMISSION LOSSES TABLE}(\text{Time}))$$

The desired electricity generation serves as input for the calculation of the desired electricity generation by technology, which is calculated by multiplying the total desired generation by the shares of generation satisfied by the respective technology.

$$\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{desired electricity generation} * \text{electricity generation shares peak demand}[\text{power generation technology}]$$

Considering the load factor and the number of hours per year, the desired electricity generation by technology is used to calculate the required electricity generation capacity for each technology.

$$\text{required electricity generation capacity by technology} = (\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] / \text{hours per year} / \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}])$$

The power generation capacity gap calculates the capacity generation gap by comparing the required power generation capacity with the currently installed capacity. The capacity gap for all technologies considered is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{power generation capacity gap}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{required electricity generation capacity by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{Power Generation Capacity Under Construction}[\text{power generation technology}]$$

The required electricity generation capacity is compared to the current power generation capacity and power generation capacity under construction to determine whether there is a capacity gap.

The stock of power generation capacity under construction is changed by the construction rate and the completion rate. The construction rate is increasing the stock level and calculated by dividing the power generation capacity gap by the time to process capacity orders. The completion rate is an outflow of power generation capacity under construction and an inflow to power generation capacity. The completion rate is defined as a fixed order delay based on the construction rate and the construction time of all technologies, based on the assumption that capacity becomes functional once the construction is completed. Power generation capacity is increased by the completion rate, and decreased by decommissioning, whereby decommissioning is calculated as a fixed delay of the completion rate and the capacity lifetime, based on the assumption that capacity depreciates after a fixed lifetime.

An additional flow captures the retirement of capacity. This flow is established to ensure that the currently installed power generation capacity is equal to the active amount of capacity required based on the desired electricity generation shares. The retirement of capacity is estimated based on the power generation potential if capacity would be utilized at full capacity (given the respective load factors) and the desired electricity generation by technology. The difference between the two represents the excess power generation with currently installed capacity.

$$\text{excess power generation with current capacity} [\text{power generation technology}] = \text{MAX}(0, \text{potential power generation with full capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] - \text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}])$$

Dividing the excess power generation by technology by the load factor and the number of hours per year yields the amount of capacity to be phased out to match current generation capacity given the desired shares of electricity generation by technology.

$$\frac{\text{capacity phase out to match required capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{excess power generation with current capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] / \text{LOAD FACTOR TIMES BASELINE}[\text{power generation technology}]/\text{hours per year}}$$

Capacity phase out divided by the time to phase out capacity constitutes the flow retirement of power generation capacity.

Electricity generation is calculated based on the power generation capacity, the load factor, and the hours per year. It represents the total amount of electricity that is produced. The following equation is used to calculate the electricity generation for all capacity types.

$$\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{power generation technology}] = \text{MAX}(\text{IF THEN ELSE} (\text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}] < \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}], \text{MIN}(\text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}], \text{desired electricity generation by technology}[\text{power generation technology}]), \text{Power Generation Capacity}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{hours per year} * \text{load factor}[\text{power generation technology}]), 0)$$

The MIN function is used to ensure that only the required amount of electricity is produced, hence to avoid overproduction. It compares the current generation potential, by technology, to the desired electricity generation, by technology. If the potential generation is higher, the MIN function ensures that the technology in question does not produce more electricity than demanded. The MAX function is used to avoid that electricity production can take negative values in case of integration errors that may occur through the retirement of capacity.

The total electricity generation rate represents the sum of electricity generation from all types of capacity and is calculated by using a SUM function to add up the electricity production of all technology subscripts. The share of renewable generation is calculated as the sum of renewable generation divided by total generation across all technologies, as represented by the following equation

$$\text{share of renewable generation} = \text{ZIDZ}(\text{SUM}(\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{all renewables!}]), \text{SUM}(\text{electricity generation rate}[\text{power generation technology!}]))$$

8.11 Employment from power generation

The employment module captures the employment that is generated through the construction and maintenance of energy generating capacity. It allows for observing the impact that different energy pathways have on the total employment of the energy sector. Furthermore, it also captures the employment that is generated through the extraction of fossil fuels.

Table 60 provides an overview over key variables of the module, and lists the reports and documents that are used for the parameterization of the module.

Table 60: Key variables and sources in the Employment module

Name of variable	Type
O&M employment per MW of thermal capacity	Time series

O&M employment per MW of hydropower capacity	Time series
O&M employment per MW of RE capacity	Time series
employment per MW of thermal capacity	Time series
employment per MW of hydropower capacity	Time series
employment per MW of RE capacity	Time series

Employment from the energy sector is divided into employment from the construction of capacity and employment from the operation and maintenance of capacity. Figure 94 shows the variables that are used to calculate the employment that is generated by the energy sector. The variable electricity employment represents the sum of employment that is generated by construction and operations and maintenance per capacity type.

Figure 94: Causes tree of electricity employment

Construction employment is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{construction employment} = \text{Power Generation Capacity Under Construction[technology]} * \text{construction employment per mw of capacity[technology]} * \text{FRACTION OF CONSTRUCTION TAKING PLACE DOMESTICALLY}$$

The power generation capacity under construction is multiplied by a construction multiplier per MW of capacity and the fraction of construction taking place domestically. The fraction of local construction corrects for the manufacturing that is not generated domestically if power generation capacity is imported.

O&M employment is calculated by multiplying power generation capacity by the O&M employment per MW of capacity. The variables construction employment per mw of capacity and O&M employment per MW of capacity are time series variables that contain employment multipliers for each type of capacity.

Total O&M employment and total construction employment are the sum of the generated employment in operations and maintenance, and the construction of capacity respectively, for all capacity types. The variables total thermal and nuclear employment, total hydropower employment and total renewable employment are indicator variables that provide an overview of the number of people that are employed based on capacity types.

8.12 CO₂e emissions

The CO₂e emissions module calculates country-wide CO₂ emissions from all sectors. The module provides information about the development of CO₂e emission over time and allows for the assessment of policy impacts on CO₂e emissions per capita and the social cost of carbon.

Total annual CO₂e emissions are calculated as the sum of emissions from energy, industry (IPPU) and waste, livestock, managed soils, and land use (land use, land use change and forestry, or LULUCF). The variables underlying the calculation of total and sectoral CO₂e emissions are illustrated in the causes tree in Figure 95.

Figure 95: Causes tree total CO2e emissions

Emissions from industry are calculated based on industry real GDP and emission intensity per unit of industry real GDP.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{co2e emissions from industry and waste} = \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE (LOW IMPACT DEVELOPMENT POLICY SWITCH=1, real GDP industry * industry emissions per unit of} \\
 & \quad \text{industry real GDP(Time) * (1 - LCD emission reductions from improved processes table(Time)),} \\
 & \text{IF THEN ELSE (LOW IMPACT DEVELOPMENT POLICY SWITCH=2, real GDP industry * industry emissions per unit of} \\
 & \quad \text{industry real GDP(Time) * (1 - NZE emission reductions from improved processes table(Time)), real GDP industry *} \\
 & \quad \text{industry emissions per unit of industry real GDP(Time))}
 \end{aligned}$$

The GE reduction in industry emission intensity is a policy variable and used to allow for the simulation of policies that would reduce emissions from industry and to assess their impacts on total CO2e emissions. If the GE policy switch is active (value of “1”), the model will simulate a reduction in industry emission intensity. This reduction is a policy input and will be informed by national plans related to reducing emissions from the industrial sector.

CO2e emissions from energy are calculated as the sum of emissions generated across all sectors through the use of energy (see energy demand module) but the non-energy use sector.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{total co2e emissions from energy} = \\
 & \text{(SUM(coal emissions[sector excluding nonenergy use!]) + SUM(electricity emissions[sector excluding nonenergy} \\
 & \quad \text{use!]) + SUM(natural gas emissions[sector excluding nonenergy use!]) + SUM(petroleum emissions[sector excluding} \\
 & \quad \text{nonenergy use!]) + SUM(biofuels and waste emissions[sector excluding nonenergy use!]))}
 \end{aligned}$$

GHG emissions from livestock calculated as the sum of CH4 emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management and N2O emissions from manure management.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{co2e emissions from livestock} = \\
 & \text{co2e emissions from livestock ch4 + co2e emissions from manure management}
 \end{aligned}$$

Livestock related CH4 and N2O emissions as described above are converted into CO2e using a conversion factor for the GHG equivalent of CH4 and N2O respectively.

CO2e emissions from managed soils are calculated as the sum of total N2O emissions from managed soils and CO2 emissions from urea and limestone application.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{co2e emissions from managed soils} = \\
 & \text{((total n2o emissions from managed soils / UNIT CORRECTION FOR N2O * N2O TO CO2) + co2 emissions from urea} \\
 & \quad \text{and limestone) / KG PER TON}
 \end{aligned}$$

The cause tree in Figure 96 illustrates the variables used to calculate total N2O emissions from managed soils.

Figure 96: Causes tree total N2O emissions from managed soils

Total annual CO_{2e} emissions serve for the calculation of the CO_{2e} emissions per capita and the country-level social cost of carbon. CO_{2e} emissions per capita are calculated by dividing total CO_{2e} emissions by population. The social cost of carbon on a country level is based on total CO_{2e} emissions and the social cost of carbon per ton of carbon emitted (Nordhaus, 2017). GEM does not assume an escalation of SCC as proposed by Nordhaus (2017), indicating that the SCC per ton of CO_{2e} emitted remains constant at USD 31 per ton throughout the simulation.

$$\text{annual social cost of carbon} = \text{total co2e emissions} * \text{SOCIAL COST OF CARBON PER TON} * \text{EXCHANGE RATE USD TO LEMPIRAS}$$

8.13 Air pollution from energy consumption and power generation

GEM estimates the occurrence of air pollutants from final domestic energy consumption and power generation. In total, GEM estimates 11 pollutants across energy sources and sectors. The emission factors were obtained from the emission factor database of the LEAP Integrated Benefits Calculator (IBC), which is publicly available². Air pollutants considered in GEM are:

- CO₂
- CO
- NO_x
- N₂O
- NMVOC
- CH₄
- PM₁₀
- PM_{2.5}
- Black carbon
- Organic Carbon
- Ammonia (NH₃)

Air pollutants for energy consumption and power generation are calculated separately. Air pollutants from final energy consumption are calculated by multiplying the total final energy demand (by fuel source) by a respective emission factor by type of fuel and sector. For example, pm₁₀ emissions from biomass use, for each sector considered, are calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{pm10 emissions from biomass[sector]} = \text{normalized biofuels and waste demand[sector]} * \text{PM10 EMISSIONS PER TJ OF BIOMASS BY SECTOR[sector]/KG PER TON}$$

The same approach is used for all other fuel types (coal, petroleum, natural gas). Air pollutants from power generation are calculated by multiplying the fuel used for the generation of electricity by respective emissions per TJ of fuel used multiplier.

² <https://leap.sei.org/default.asp?action=IBC>

$$\frac{\text{fuel use for power generation in tj}[\text{power generation technology}]}{\text{fuel use per mwh by technology new}[\text{power generation technology}] * \text{electricity generation rate}[\text{power generation technology}]}$$

The emission factors used for the estimation of air pollutants from energy consumption and power generation are summarized in Table 61.

Table 61: Overview of air pollution multipliers for energy consumption and power generation

Fuel type/Sector	CO2	CO	Nox	NMVOC	CH4	PM10	PM2.5	Black Carbon	Organic Carbon	N2O	NH3
	Ton/TJ	kg/TJ									
<i>Coal</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	94.6	2,610	34	484	300	490.1	440.4	72.85	196.4	0	38.74
<i>Commercial</i>	94.6	931	173	88.8	10	117	108	6.9	5.2	1.5	0.0093
<i>Industry</i>	94.6	931	173	88.8	10	117	108	6.9	5.2	1.5	0.0093
<i>Transport</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
<i>Petroleum</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	67.46	93	306	20	10	21	18	10.1	2.89	1.51	0.108
<i>Commercial</i>	74.1	130	942	50	10	96	96	40	28	0.6	0.168
<i>Industry</i>	74.1	66	513	25	3	20	20	11.2	3.6	0.6	0.154
<i>Transport</i>	69.3	5,808	644.2	741.81	33	161.64	161.64	9.27	116.38	3.2	31.03
<i>Natural gas</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	56.1	26	51	1.9	5	1.2	1.2	0.065	0.54	0.1	0.181
<i>Commercial</i>	56.1	29	74	23	5	0.78	0.78	0.03	0.26	0.942	1.214
<i>Industry</i>	56.1	29	74	23	1	0.78	0.78	0.03	0.26	0.1	1.214
<i>Transport</i>	56.1	271.7	543.48	12.14	92	0.725	0.725	0.036	0.326	2.72	N/A
<i>Biofuels and waste</i>											
<i>Residential</i>	95.6	4,753	134.6	1,654	300	512.35	409.88	51.24	178.4	134.57	53.7
<i>Commercial</i>	112	570	91	300	300	143	140	39.2	72	4	37

<i>Industry</i>	112	570	91	300	30	143	140	39.2	72	4	37
<i>Transport</i>	79.6	5,808	51	0.69	18	1.9	1.9	0.16	0	0	0
<i>Power generation (by fuel type)</i>											
<i>Fuel and diesel oil</i>	77.4	15.1	142	2.3	3	25.2	19.3	0.957	0.359	0.6	0.101
<i>Cogeneration</i>	77.4	15.1	142	2.3	3	25.2	19.3	0.957	0.359	0.6	0.101
<i>Natural gas</i>	565.1	39	89	2.6	1	0.89	0.89	0.022	0.022	0.1	1.829
<i>Coal</i>	96.1	8.7	247	1.4	1	7.9	3.2	0.083	0.167	1.5	0.012
<i>Waste incineration</i>	91.7	90	81	7.31	30	155	133	1.444	0.222	4	0.222

9 CONCLUSIONS

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of the transition towards a CBBE, examining its implications across four key industries—construction, plastics, textiles, and chemicals—and assessing the broader systemic impacts of adopting bio-based solutions. By leveraging system dynamics models, this study captures the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of the transition, mapping the interactions between material demand, consumption patterns, life cycle impacts, and policy interventions. The models track resource flows from raw material extraction to final disposal, incorporating aspects such as energy consumption, recycling rates, and cascading use of bio-based materials. Through this approach, the report provides insights into how different policy pathways can shape sustainability outcomes and optimize resource efficiency.

The analysis spans three distinct scenarios, each representing varying levels of ambition in achieving a circular bio-based economy. The BAU scenario extrapolates current trends without additional circular economy policies, highlighting the risks of continued resource depletion and high waste generation. The Bio-Transition scenario integrates existing policies aimed at fostering a gradual shift toward circularity, demonstrating incremental improvements in material efficiency, waste reduction, and bio-based adoption. Finally, the Bio-Revolution scenario represents an ambitious transformation, where strong policies and investments drive a rapid and comprehensive transition to full circularity and bio-based practices, significantly reducing environmental pressures while reshaping industrial processes and consumption habits.

Findings indicate that transitioning to bio-based materials presents clear economic and environmental advantages. The Bio-Transition scenario shows notable value addition compared to BAU, driven by increased resource efficiency, reduced environmental externalities, and enhanced circular material flows. The Bio-Revolution scenario amplifies these benefits, showcasing the potential for higher economic returns, lower emissions, and reduced reliance on fossil-based materials, even as stricter resource efficiency measures limit overall material consumption. However, the transition also raises the demand for biomass, which must be carefully managed to ensure sustainable production. The report highlights that this demand can be met through the strategic use of marginal and abandoned land, preventing adverse impacts on food security, deforestation, and biodiversity. Sustainable biomass sourcing, supported by targeted land-use policies, technological advancements, and supply chain optimization, will be crucial in balancing economic benefits with ecological integrity.

At the national level, broader policy integration is necessary to ensure that industrial shifts align with overarching sustainability goals. The analysis underscores how policies extending beyond individual sectors—such as biofuels in transport, enhanced recycling efforts, and the expansion of renewable energy sources—can create synergies across industries, reinforcing the benefits of circularity and decarbonization. The interactions between industrial transformation and national strategies highlight the importance of cross-sectoral coordination, ensuring that energy, material, and waste policies work together to maximize economic and environmental gains. However, the transition also entails trade-offs, including land-use considerations, employment shifts in traditional industries, and potential economic disruptions. Effective policy design, including targeted support for affected industries and workers, will be essential in mitigating these challenges and fostering a just and inclusive transition.

Ultimately, this report underscores the transformative potential of the CBBE, demonstrating that a well-designed policy framework can drive economic growth, reduce environmental pressures, and support long-term sustainability objectives.

Concerning possible improvements of the analysis, more research is needed regarding data on employment metrics across various activities within the bio-based industry and value chain, rather than relying on proxies. This will help more accurately assess the sector's impact on job creation and workforce distribution (e.g. in relation to the reduction in manufacturing jobs, and an increase in materials management jobs). Additionally, it is important to expand the model to incorporate water pollution metrics, which will provide a more holistic view of the environmental impacts (both desirable and undesirable) associated with bio-based product production. This expanded analysis should include examining the effects of biomass cultivation and processing on water quality, including potential runoff, contamination, and resource usage, as well as the avoided impact emerging from moving away from conventional practices and transitioning to lower production (e.g. in the textile sector). However, as this study is based on a national model, its scope limits the ability to assess implications for global value chains, where bio-based material flows and labour dynamics may differ significantly. Moreover, water runoff is an inherently spatial issue, and a spatially explicit modelling approach would be needed to properly capture localized effects and better inform regional water management strategies. By integrating these refinements, future iterations of the model could offer a more holistic perspective on the social and environmental impacts of the transition to a CBBE, supporting more informed and context-specific decision-making.

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- ANNEX 1

This annex presents and adaptation of the policy portfolios prepared in Deliverable 4.1 for the Bio-Transition and Bio-Revolution scenario for the four industries: construction, plastics, textiles and chemicals. The policies selected from the policy portfolio in D4.1 are the ones that are specific enough and can be simulated with the industry models described in sections 4, 5, 6, and 7 of this report.

Construction Industry - Bio-Transition scenario

Table 62: Construction industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Transition scenario

Year	Demand (buildings renovation)	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1. Improve materials productivity at 1.5% per year (BMUV, 2020).		1. The preparing for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled (European Commission, 2023). 2. Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparation for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008). 3. The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, a maximum of 80% comes from primary raw material. For non-bio-based plastic in 50% (European Commission, 2023). 4. The use of primary raw material in buildings renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 90% come from primary raw material. For non-bio-based plastic in 75% (European Commission, 2023).
2030	1. At least 2% of annual energy renovation in buildings, involving these key principles: (i) energy efficiency, (ii) affordability, (iii) decarbonization and integration of renewables, (iv) life-cycle thinking and circularity, and (v)		1. Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse	

D4.3 Presenting high health and environmental standards	<p>high health and environmental standards (European Commission, 2020).</p> <p>2.double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector, and renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually (European Commission, 2021).</p>	documentation of the model	<p>gas emissions into a carbon sink (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>2. climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019).</p>	
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Construction industry, Bio-Revolution scenario

Table 63: Construction industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Revolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1. Improve materials productivity at 2% per year (BMUV, 2020).		1. Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparation for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (Official Journal of the European Union, 2008).
2030		<p>1. At least 2% of annual energy renovation (European Commission, 2020).</p> <p>2. (...) double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector. (...) renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>3. 5 Mt of CO2 should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030. (25)(including vacancy management of buildings) (European Commission, 2021)</p> <p>4. Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils).</p>	<p>1. Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>2. climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, 2019).</p>	<p>1. The preparation for re-use or recycling of construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>2. The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 80% come from primary raw material. For non-bio-based plastic in 50% (European Commission, 2023).</p> <p>3. The use of primary raw material in buildings renovation is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. For bio-based materials, maximum 90% come from primary raw material. For non-bio-based plastic in 75% (European Commission, 2023).</p>
2050		1. Adapted policy goal: (...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) (European Commission, 2021). To about 1,5% of worldwide market in the sectors of construction, plastics and textiles		1. Adapted policy goal As many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists.

Table 64: Plastics industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Transition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025	1. Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).	1. Improve raw materials productivity (1.5% per year) (BMUV, 2020).	1. use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023) 2. from 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019).	1. member states shall set up separate collections at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018). 2. By 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 3. by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 4. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
2028			1. From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging;(a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).	
2030			1. from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019). 2. Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).	1. Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 2. Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 55 % of plastic; (ii) 30 % of wood; (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 3. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
2040			1. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of	

D4.3 Presenting the results of all simulations and documentation of the model			packaging: (a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).	
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Plastics industry, Bio-Revolution scenario

Table 65: Plastics industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Revolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025	1. Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019) 2. Annual reduction in growth of plastic: 1,5 %/year (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018).	1. Improve raw materials productivity (2% per year) (BMUV, 2020)	1. use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (European Commission, 2023). 2. from 2025, beverage bottles manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019)	1. member states shall set up separate collections at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018). 2. By 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated is recycled (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 3. by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated is recycled: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 4. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
2028			1. From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (European Commission, 2023).	
2030			1. from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (The European Parliament and of the European Council, 2019). 2. Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles;	1. Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 7,5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (European Commission, 2023). 2. Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in

D4.3 Presenting the results of all simulations and documentation of the model			
		(c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).	packaging waste generated: (i) 60 % of plastic; (ii) 35 % of wood; (European Environment Agency, 2022b). 3. Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/year (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2024).
2040		1. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b) (European Environment Agency, 2022b).	1. Mechanical recycling: 45% and chemical recycling of 15% (adapted from (Circular Economy Roadmap for Germany, 2021) & (Transition Agenda - Circular Economy, 2018))
2050		1. Adapted or added policy: As much as possible no fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU-Carbon Capture and Utilization.)	

Textile Industry, Bio-Transition scenario

Table 66: Textile industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Transition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1.ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO2 in the non-ETS sectors (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022).		1. Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022 (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021)
2026				1. Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs" (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2030	1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects" (European Commission, 2022).		1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects" (European Commission, 2022).	1. Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017).

D4.3 Presenting the results	2.to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products (European Commission, 2022).	documentation of the model		
2035	1.the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).			1.ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).

Textile Industry, Bio-Revolution scenario

Table 67: Textile industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Revolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2025		1.ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO2 in the non-ETS sectors (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2022).		1. Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2026				1.Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs" (National recovery and resilience plan 2021-2026, 2021).
2027			1. Adapted or added policy goal: The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%.	2. Adapted or added policy goal: 30% of resources, materials and products placed on the textile market will be recycled after collection – if direct reuse is no longer possible. 3. Adapted or added policy goal: 10% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused after collection.
2030	1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (European Commission, 2022). 2.to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products (European Commission, 2022).		1.establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (European Commission, 2022). 2. Adapted or added policy goal: supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer) 1. Adapted or added policy goal:	1. Adapted or added policy goal: In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles. 2. Adapted or added policy goal: 50% of resources, materials and products placed on the market will be recycled after collection – if direct reuse is no longer possible. 3. Adapted or added policy goal: 15% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused in the after collection. 4. Adapted or added policy goal:

	D4.3 Presenting the results of all simulations and documentation of the model		In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles.	Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion
2035	<p>1. the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).</p> <p>2. Adapted or added policy goal: Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain</p>		<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal: The aim is to halve the ecological footprint of the textile industry with regard to emissions, water usage, chemicals and microplastics</p>	<p>5.ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system (National Strategy for Circular Economy, 2022).</p> <p>6. Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect the ECONOMY, SOCIETY and the ENVIRONMENT, 2017)</p>
2050			<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal: Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector</p>	<p>1. Adapted or added policy goal: Full circular textile material flows</p>

Chemical Industry, Bio-Transition scenario

Table 68: Chemical industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Transition scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2030		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Reduction of 5 Mt of CO2 emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021). 3. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023). 1. 20% of the carbon used should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030 (European Commission, 2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023). 	
2050		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. 0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020). 3. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 75% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023). 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are 80% circular (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023). 1. To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised.(...) (European Commission, 2020).

Chemical Industry, Bio-Revolution scenario

Table 69: Chemical industry policy portfolio scenarios adapted from D4.1, Bio-Revolution scenario

Year	Demand	Efficiency (materials, energy)	Switching (fuel, materials)	Recycling
2030		<p>1. reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2023).</p> <p>2.Reduction of 5 Mt of CO2 emissions through frontrunner projects (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>1. Adapted or added policy goal: At least 30% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030</p>	<p>2.Consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p>	
2040				<p>1. To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised (European Commission, 2020).</p>
2045		<p>1.0% pollution for air, water, and soil (European Commission, 2020).</p>		
2050		<p>1.reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact in 75% (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p> <p>1. Adapted or added policy goal: At least 40% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources 2050.</p>		<p>1.In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular (Netherlands Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2023).</p>

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